

**Trust Evaluation and Management in
E-commerce Systems using Artificial
Intelligence and Emerging Technologies**

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Abstract

The internet market has a lack of physical presence and physical indication; therefore, it is more complex and difficult to bring trust between sellers and buyers. This is what distinguishes it as a big obstacle for businesses engaged in the several applications of e-commerce platforms. Moreover, it is essential to recognize influences, which enables to create customer interest in e-commerce, and consumers can feel reliable and get interested to buy on an e-commerce platform frequently. Therefore, there is an alarming demand to deal with the aforementioned issues and how to create a trust evaluation-based model that provides feasible support for both current and past sales. The proposed research comprises several trust hypotheses, a business case review, and primary data selections to establish a more reliable and diverse database. The purpose was to examine customer trust from a personal perspective and to decide if the variables of trust are positively influenced by personal characteristics, culture, and experience.

The overall objectives of this proposed research are to examine that how to build trust in online markets such as in e-commerce applications, also to investigate the impact of trust between sellers and buyers during their active interaction and online trust formation process. This work is particularly concerned with how different types of users (online stores and internet users) use trust in their trust-building practices. The relationship between trust variables and risks associated with trust adoption was not provided by researchers in existing work. Researchers have failed to explore the dilemma in a multifaceted and multidimensional manner. To deal

with these issues, the first contribution provides an effective method that considers three dimensions that play important roles in any online transaction to help the buyers to detect fraud. This method measures the similarity between the new transaction and the past transactions in the products types dimension, the number of the products sold dimension, and the transactions amount dimension.

Our second contribution utilises the trust evaluation between the transactions by measuring the similarities between the new transactions of a purchaser and the previous sales record of a buyer. The proposed model is capable to normalise several user evaluations after following their evaluation criteria, which continuously changes with time. This model also investigates trust and reputation for all users based on the general merchant rating and the aspects of the transaction time, both have a significant role in any online transaction to help customers gain trust in online shopping and identify the frauds. Overall, our model based on eBay and Epinions transaction datasets derives stable trust values from immutable transactions.

Our third contribution is based on mining customer's comments and feedback expressed in free text. We introduce an algorithm for extracting input on measurements weights, integrating natural language processing methods, information extraction, and subject/topic modelling. Evaluation based on Amazon data sets enables us to demonstrate that order of importance for our predefined dimensions is Rating, Product Type, Price, Time interval, and Quantity Sold.

The final contribution is designed in collaboration with the Software-Defined Networking (SDN) and blockchain. SDN allows versatile implementation and advancement of modern networking applications due to the programmability approach, and decoupling of the control plane from the data plane, the concept and way of developing and operating interconnected networks has evolved dramatically and reduced the obstacles in the e-commerce markets. Moreover, SDN also experiences a variety of challenges, such as trust limitation and single point failure in a distributed

network framework. Blockchain-based SDN has become an evolving architecture to protect a distributed network framework with the introduction of blockchain applications. In this model, the major objective of our research is to optimize the security between various E-commerce applications/businesses, also to mitigate the single point failure of security vulnerabilities via Blockchain-based SDN framework. Our proposed model also utilises the trust between E-commerce applications with the help of blockchain-based trust key distribution.

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Declaration

I, Nasser Alsharif, declare that this thesis titled, “Trust Evaluation and Management in E-commerce Systems using Artificial Intelligence and Emerging Technologies” and the work presented in it are my own. I confirm that:

1. This work was done wholly or mainly while in candidature for a research degree at this University.
2. Where any part of this thesis has previously been submitted for a degree or any other qualification at this University or any other institution, this has been clearly stated.
3. Where I have consulted the published work of others, this is always clearly attributed.
4. Where I have quoted from the work of others, the source is always given. Except for such quotations, this thesis is entirely my own work.
5. I have acknowledged all main sources of help.
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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Overview of E-commerce Trust and Reputation

The trustworthiness of a purchaser is very significant to potential buyers in e-commerce contexts, particularly when the dealer is unknown to everyone. Most current trust evaluation processes produce a single value that reflects a seller's general reliability without considering transaction reference details. For such an outcome as a reputation indicator, a buyer could be easily brainwashed by a deceptive seller in a transaction that involves the well-known value imbalance dilemma, in which a fraudulent seller builds a high-level reputation by selling low-cost goods and then manipulates customers by convincing others to consume more expensive goods.

A successful trust analysis technique in an e-commerce setting will ensure both sellers and customers get the most out of their transactions. Furthermore, significant variations in sale rates have been found between emerging sellers (no reputation) and sellers with a great reputation in terms of economic benefits. Consequently,

dealers with outstanding likeability are often more likely than those with bad trustworthiness to sell goods effectively. As a result, trust has attracted a lot of attention from researchers in recent years, leading to the creation of numerous trust management solutions [84].

There are two kinds of trust protection systems currently available. The first maintains trust between peers specifically through active interaction. The second form is focused on the node's internal direct insights and feedback from other devices in the system. The use of a recommendation-based trust technique will help nodes detect misbehaving nodes before they communicate, mitigating a potentially negative encounter [76].

Trust is essential at every step in our daily lives, which also makes it a crucial factor in society. It is difficult to explain what trust means to us in just a few words, but some options include honesty, trust, faith, surety, belief, etc. According to [64], [2] trustworthiness can be equated with a social context in some ways, for example, by referring to the interaction history, social reputation, word of mouth from a reliable third party, or certification, product, or service. Trust can be defined in different ways because of its nature: the context of trust's sensitivity indicates that its definition might change with environment and time [44].

The reputation mechanism, which is a concept related to trust, is used as one of the most common ways to measure the trustworthiness in certain environments.

The reputation component - also known as the trust-related term, is used in some environments as one of the most well-known approaches to measure trustworthiness. The Compact Oxford English dictionary has described this as a form of belief, which depicts that credibility is "beliefs or opinions generally held about someone or something" [130]. Reference can also be made on the basis that credibility is a concept of trust, although it has marginally unique importance, which can be utilized without misconception.

The authors in [62], reputation has been described as "an assumption of an agent's behaviour based on information or impressions of his past behaviour". A few sites for e-services like eBay utilize a fundamental trust assurance framework to give clients some trust information before they are in some deal. The purchasers can likewise rate the merchant by giving him/her any positive or negative rating after any purchase. During past transitions, these reviews are obtained from customers, where only one input is used to estimate the level of trust between various merchants.

It is also worth mentioning that reputation is a concept related to trust but holds a slightly different meaning, so the two can be used without confusing them. The authors in [63] has defined reputation as "an expectation about an agent's behaviour based on information about or observations of its past behaviour"

Some e-services websites such as eBay use simple mechanism of trust management to give some information of trust to buyers before being in any transaction. The buyers can also rate the seller after any transaction by giving him/her (Negative, Neutral or Positive). These ratings are accumulated from the buyers and single feedback is computed to show the trust status of the seller over the past transactions.

There are many models proposed by researchers depending on only the past transactions to represent the reputation of a seller. However, most of these models show only the general status of trust while the buyer might have concerns about the new transactions. The buyers might not rely on this trust value, which only infers to the trust level of a past transaction. As a result, the buyers might be vulnerable to be attacked by malicious sellers. For example, a good reputation of a malicious seller can be simply built up by selling cheap products or services and then starting cheating the buyers after obtaining a good reputation. This kind of attack has been mentioned and named by [68] as the value imbalance problem.

In recent years, E-commerce, along with economic globalisation and the advancement of the Internet, has seen its dramatic growth. E-commerce exchange and

distribution require partnerships amongst E-commerce supply chain participants. Developing trust among supply chain participants has become a crucial problem [70]. Because of the variations between countries in culture, legislation, and philosophy [129], the issue of trust could not be easily rectified. The implementation of blockchain technologies provides several new thoughts on the administration of the E-commerce supply chain [32]. Within the sense of cross-border E-commerce, participants' credit measurement is their most significant barrier to achieving a deal [22]. Blockchain's fundamental importance is the development of open and straightforward algorithm based laws, and the creation of a trusted network, maintaining business confidentiality and gaining identity legitimacy in dynamic environments [133].

There are some trust approaches are based on E-commerce communication and attacks detection in Software Define Network (SDN). The SDN is a modern networking infrastructure that has received a lot of coverage in recent decades for delivering security in the E-commerce industry. Protection, on the other hand, remains a major issue in the E-commerce industry, despite many proposals for enhancements is a new network model that uses a methodology called network programmability to ease network creation and manipulation [33]. SDN controller is capable to deal with majority of networking tasks with adaptive and effective ways. The controller's job is to have an abstract view of the whole network through a GUI, handle distributed network resources, and make logically centralized decisions about resource management [120].

1.2 Research Motivation

The trustworthiness of a seller is a critical issue in the decision-making process prior to a purchase in e-commerce settings [140]. eBay's or Amazon ranking system is a clear example of how to manage a seller's value or truthfulness. However,

a simplistic trust protection scheme like this is vulnerable to a variety of frauds perpetrated by fraudulent vendors . A dishonest trader, for example, may establish a positive credibility by offering high-quality, low-priced goods.

If a good reputation has been established, s/he can mislead customers by convincing them to purchase more premium items by either failing to deliver the purchased products or delivering a counterfeit. This is known as the value mismatch dilemma in the literary works [66, 29, 58, 67, 57], and such malicious sellers are referred to as traitors. Similarly, [166] reports on a number of real-world events. For example, an Australian traitor scammed people out of more than AU\$10,000 by trading legitimately by offering cheap goods to build a good reputation before selling costly products. In the same way, a Californian traitor was able to receive a strong positive feedback rating before defrauding.

The trust evaluation mechanism should be able to prevent fraudulent behaviour by peers during online transactions, such as the value imbalance problem perpetuated by malicious sellers. This kind of problem can be prevented by considering shared factors among online transactions, such as the similarity between the transactions, the contexts of the transactions, and the inheritances of the transactions. Besides, there is a demand for a trust evaluation mechanism that takes into account not only the general status of the trust value by considering the past transactions but also the probable status of the trust value as determined by future transactions.

Most of the existing models mainly demonstrate the general status of trust, whereas several e-commerce customers raise some questions especially for the reliable transaction with trust. Many buyers feel unsatisfied after depending on such limited trust factors, that primarily refers to the degree of trust of the previous transaction. As a result, such buyers or e-commerce consumers will be targeted by deceptive vendors. The internet market has a lack of physical presence and physical indication; therefore, it is more complex and difficult to bring trust between sellers and buyers.

This is what distinguishes as a big obstacle for businesses engaged in the several applications of e-commerce platform. Moreover, it is essential to recognize influences, which enables to create customer interest in e-commerce, and consumers can feel reliable and get interested to buy on an e-commerce platform frequently. Therefore, there is an alarming demand to deal with the aforementioned issues and how to create a trust evaluation-based model that provides feasible support for both current and past sales.

There is a considerable demand for a method that considers the contexts of online transactions since most models do not consider these contexts in their trust evaluations. Every online transaction has different contexts, so the same transaction needs to be evaluated differently concerning these contexts. Contexts such as the product type, the number of product sold, the transaction amount, time to handle the transactions and the overall ratings, and the value imbalance problem can be found in any of the contexts. Therefore, the trust evaluation mechanism should include the contexts of any online transaction to be able to prevent this kind of attack.

A key concern is related to provide cost-effective and significant security implementation with an online e-commerce model in a distributed environment. According to authors [133], the issue of trust could not be easily rectified. The implementation of blockchain technologies provides several new thoughts on the administration of the E-commerce supply chain [32]. Within the sense of cross-border E-commerce, participants' credit measurement is their most significant barrier to achieving a deal [22]. Blockchain's fundamental importance is the development of open and straightforward algorithm-based laws, and the creation of a trusted network, maintaining business confidentiality and gaining identity legitimacy in dynamic environments [133].

Most of the existing approaches for trust-based E-commerce communication and

attacks detection in Software Define Network (SDN) are limited due to such challenges as below:

- **Centralization:** Many attack vector identification techniques rely on a centralized paradigm, in which an attacker is classified by a centralized cloud server that runs an intrusion detection system [39]. Because the whole infrastructure incorporates a large number of users, these methods are hard to handle. Moreover, the central cloud would remain unreliable due to capacity limitations, high processing rates, high latency, and single-point loss.

- **Big data problem:**

Because it includes a large quantity of data to be collected from communication equipment and the system for real-time data processing, identifying security threats is a big data challenge. Many real-time data sets allow for a specific decision to be made in order to identify actions. Extracting and processing real-time data in E-commerce systems, on the other hand, would be quite costly. Besides, an injecting malicious incorrect information, such that the bandwidth usage and redundancy [106]. Both of these problems appear to limit the precision of threat classification in E-commerce applications

- **Lack of privacy:** The most recent threat detection methods do not prioritize data security. They process data without the agreement of the owner in a variety of ways. Furthermore, present methods of detecting assaults are difficult to acquire adequate data owing to the issue of user privacy, resulting in erroneous identification estimates. [105].

The latest E-commerce platform implementation contains its vast amounts of data relating to customers, goods, and distributors. The data collection, maintenance, and examination methods have grown significantly. The E-commerce network has the inherent benefit of integrating data from upstream producers or vendors, middle network operators, and downstream customers [162]. The incorporation of

blockchain and E-commerce development also provides a variety of unanswered questions. Accomplishing verification of product details in a blockchain-based structure demands for a modern framework architecture, involving technical expertise on E-commerce management for the supply chain. The larger amount of data produced from E-commerce in the blockchain demands a more effective model of architecture. Also, it is very essential to address the protection related concerns inside the blockchain-based shared communication protocol. New algorithms for information protection and key control approaches should be built to secure data protection within E-commerce applications.

There were several controversies in the existing research on the problem of examining this discussion in a realistic situation, for the reasons stated:

- Trust is difficult to define and evaluate due to the fact of different users' perspectives.
- Researchers in existing work has not provided the relationship between trust factors and risks associated with trust implementation.
- Investigators have struggled to examine the issue in a multifaceted and multidimensional way [141].
- A single point failure in a distributed network framework can cause major loss such as the whole enterprise run down with the failure of that point.

1.3 Research Objectives

The primary aim of this study was to investigate the importance of consumer trust and how it is affected by E-commerce applications. Furthermore, this was important to recognize the important components that E-commerce firms need to monitor and respond to influencing consumer behaviour and the decision-making process. The

purpose was not only to examine customer trust from a personal perspective and to decide if the variables of trust are positively influenced by personal characteristics, culture, and experience or only by the technical factors generated by the medium of E-commerce. As a result, the study includes several trust hypotheses, business case review, and primary data selections to establish a more reliable and diverse database.

The key objectives of this proposed study are to explore how to create trust in online markets, such as in E-commerce applications, as well as the effect of trust between sellers and buyers during active engagement and the online trust creation process. In our thesis work, we mainly interested in how various groups of users (online stores and internet users) use trust in their trust-building activities. In addition to this, the further goal was to find effective and feasible solutions to the issues raised in the academic researchers.

The proposed research incorporates the following activities:

1. Proposed a method that considers three dimensions: the product type, the number of the product sold, and the transaction amount.
2. Suggested a hierarchical tree based on the eCl@ss standard category (a classification system for products and services) that includes the level of the products, the product type code, price, product type, transaction time and quantity sold.
3. Propose a method that considers two dimensions, which are transaction time, and overall ratings.
4. Proposed an algorithm for mining feedback comments for dimensions weights, combining techniques of natural language processing, opinion mining and topic modeling. Experiments on Amazon data demonstrate that order of importance for our predefined dimensions is Rating, Product Type, Price,

Time interval and Quantity Sold.

5. Proposed a model, in collaboration with SDN and blockchain, which enhance the various E-commerce applications security such as single point failure, also helps to evaluate the trust between E-commerce applications with the help of blockchain-based trust key distribution.

1.4 Problem Statement and Proposed Models

Physical indicators, such as the appearance of consumer items in the store and direct connection with the selling personnel associated with consumers, provide dependable and obligatory confidence in traditional retail environments. The customer perceives E-commerce apps with a digital context as more trustworthy when purchasing items; nevertheless, the majority of consumers do not perceive such trust from E-commerce applications with a digital context. Although the internet market has a lack of physical presence and physical indication, therefore it is more complex and difficult to bring trust between sellers and buyers. Due to such limitation and lack of physical presence, this is what distinguishes as a big obstacle for businesses engaged in the several applications of E-commerce platform. Moreover, it is essential to recognize influences, which enables to create customer interest in E-commerce, and consumers can feel reliable and get interested to buy on an E-commerce platform frequently.

In e-commerce, there is a shortage of trust. Consumers that purchase online might not like internet shops because they do not even know who runs them and cannot feel and hear the things they're purchasing.

Lack of trust has been described as a major stumbling block to electronic commerce development. Many researchers have shown that a vast percentage of online shoppers terminate their purchases when allowed to submit sensitive data because they

do not trust the company. In addition to this, E-commerce applications also lack proper security. Most E-commerce applications mainly rely either single-point security such as a physical or software-based firewall or encryption methodologies, during the event of a single point failure in a distributed network framework, these E-commerce applications can cause major loss such as the whole enterprise run down with the failure of their services or data breach. To help with trust evaluation, in our research, we created a systematic framework focused on E-commerce trust analysis. Our research optimises the trust factors and proved the security against single-point failure in a distributed network framework of E-commerce.

There are several academic types of research undertaken to evaluate and determine the most valuable factors which directly influence the trust models. This is also an indirect way of determining the variables that legitimize online purchases. Some research has focused on Internet-based stores such as webshops or E-commerce applications features, mainly focus was on features which are related to products and transactions attributes [49] and security concerns [139]. Researchers in economics have discovered that regardless of an online store's attributes, infrastructure shortcomings, or a lack of government policies, the most powerful motivating factor to build E-commerce based trust [77]. When trust is there, it encourages online purchases, but when it is absent, it leads to sales refusal or no revenue.

A series of other questions have also been raised based on a study of prior study. Some research, for example, identified the factors influencing initial trust formation rather than understanding trust as a whole [22] Besides that, most of the researchers used ineffective screening methods and insufficient sample sizes [28], as well as undergraduate samples as survey subjects [112]. As a result, generalizability issues arose, as well as representativeness concerns. Furthermore, some experiments used a complex control setting in which respondents' impressions were formed based on using specific websites from research scientists. Overall, E-commerce base studies need an alarming demand to identify each influencing factor with its inter-relationship

so that main concerns can be addressed to build a trust-based model.

The reported research on a detailed description of the factors that influence e-commerce trust is very limited. As a result, E-commerce industries require an alarming demand to analyse and differentiate feasible trust factors with a real-time approach and to offer a relationship between each of these factors so that potential users can buy and sell goods and services. In addition to trust factors enlisting, E-commerce industries also require significant attention to provide a valid safeguard mechanism to prevent attackers and malicious activities in a detailed fashion. As a result, this research tackles this by compiling a list of factors based on a summary of the research literature, leading to the creation of a framework for e-commerce trust.

To overcome aforementioned issues such lack of trust, improving trust factors with cost effective solutions, and to justify the centralization, single point failure area specially in e-commerce related applications. Our research work comprises on the following outcomes such as: In this work, we initially proposed a model that can evaluate the trustworthiness value by measuring the similarity between the transaction contexts along five dimensions: the product type, the number of products sold, the transaction amount, time to handle the transactions, and the seller's overall rating. These five dimensions will be used to build a trust evaluation mechanism that can prevent the fraudulent behaviour of peers during online transactions since these behaviours have major impacts on all users of E-commerce websites.

In our research, we have also utilised all five dimensions such as the product type, the number of products sold, the transaction amount, time to handle the transactions, and the seller's overall rating. The main purpose was to analyse the provided users feedback comments, which they provide as overall opinion during purchasing order or after each transaction This feedback mining mechanism uses an algorithm for extracting input on measurements weights, integrating natural language processing

methods, information extraction and subject/topic modelling. Evaluation based on Amazon data sets enables us to demonstrate that order of importance for our predefined dimensions is Rating, Product Type, Price, Time interval and Quantity Sold.

Many other trust models depend upon one measurement parameter, including such tracking collaboration in routing protocols during packet forwarding. Nevertheless, it has been shown that observing only packet communication between network nodes is insufficient to reflect the sophistication and subjectivity of trust metrics [138]. Trust models that focus solely on packet processing knowledge can only classify routes for a certain level of success and could be vulnerable to multiple attacks due to a lack of consideration for difficulties associated and multi-source evidence of trust [168].

Our research also proposes another effective security solution with an E-commerce trust evaluation. This contribution is based on the design and development of Software-Defined Networking (SDN) and blockchain. As SDN has versatile programmable implementation and advancement of modern networking applications re-configuration, based on these features our approach effectively utilises the programmability approach of SDN, which enables to utilise the Blockchain, with the implementation of blockchain applications. Main concern was to optimize the security between various E-commerce applications, also to mitigate the single point failure of security vulnerabilities. In addition to security implementation, the proposed model also utilises the trust between E-commerce applications with the help of blockchain-based trust key distribution. By implementing a blockchain-based system and presenting a group of related frameworks, strategies, and algorithms, this study addresses those limitations. The conceptual architecture, which focuses on the issue of trust between E-commerce applications also to classify the severe attacks inside such a network.

1.5 Research Contributions

To deal with the aforementioned issues, our research mainly presents the major contributions:

1. First of all, our research is based on only three different and feasible dimensions that play a significant role within E-commerce transactions, which provide the support he buyers to detect fraudulent activities. The proposed method evaluates the similarity between the new transaction and the past transactions in the products types dimension, the number of the products sold dimension and the transactions amounts dimension.
2. In our second contribution, our model further evaluates the trust factors between the transactions by considering the similarity between the transactions times of a seller and the overall rating. The proposed model can effectively be used in E-commerce applications.
3. In the third contribution, our research suggested an algorithm for mining comments or feedback from E-commerce users, then extracting input on measurements weights, integrating natural language processing methods, information extraction and subject/topic modelling. An evaluation was carried based on Amazon data sets, which enables us to demonstrate that order of importance for our predefined dimensions is Rating, Product Type, Price, Time interval and Quantity Sold.
4. In the final chapter, our research also comprises another effective security solution with an E-commerce trust evaluation. Where the model utilises the power of Software-Defined Networking (SDN) and blockchain. Based on SDN programable and reconfiguration ability the final chapter effectively utilises the easy and flexible development approach of SDN, which enables to utilise the Blockchain, with the implementation of blockchain applications. The main

objective of this proposed research focuses to optimize the security between various E-commerce applications, also to mitigate the single point failure of security vulnerabilities especially in E-commerce applications. In addition to security implementation, the proposed model also utilises the trust between E-commerce applications with the help of blockchain-based trust key distribution. Overall, our model achieves nearly a 95% attack detection rate with less than 7% false alerts, while it consumes around 10% more memory and nearly 7% of CPU overhead during full services running in lager e-commerce applications.

1.6 Outline of Research Thesis

Our research thesis comprises six chapters to support the trust evaluation in E-commerce applications.

Overview of each chapter is provided as below:

1. **Chapter - 1**, provides an overview of trust evaluation in E-commerce applications also the concerns and research challenges are also examined in this research. It also incorporates background about the methods behind it and the motives which contributed to the development of this research. In this chapter, the major aim of the proposed work is also provided along with research questions.
2. **Chapter – 2**, the idea of trust is critically presented in the subsequent chapter with the help of a detailed existing literature survey. Depending on a review of the literature, it provides an outline of the various conceptual framework of trust and addresses the feasible meaning of trust. More explicitly, this section will concentrate on E-commerce trust and the methodologies to develop it.

3. **Chapter – 3**, presents an effective method, which is capable to evaluate trust based on the trust management approach, especially with eBay E-commerce system. The proposed method considers three dimensions that play important roles in any online transaction to help the buyers to detect the frauds. This method measures the similarity between the new transaction and the past transactions in the sold product type dimension, the number of product sold dimension and the transaction amount dimension.
4. **Chapter – 4**, presents the model, which is created based on an E-commerce application that provides an authenticity attribute by avoiding data exploitation, also capable to normalise several users with the relative changes. The proposed approach can be used to calculate the trust between the transactions by measuring the similarities between the new transactions of buyers and the previous sales record of buyers based on eBay and Epinions transaction datasets. This method measures the similarity between the new transaction and the past transactions in the transactions times dimension and the overall ratings dimension.
5. **Chapter – 5**, comprises the potential user's feedback analysis and mining, in terms of investigating the feasible dimensions. The proposed method mainly focuses on a trust evaluation system with mining feedback. An algorithm for extracting input on measurement weights, integrating natural language processing methods, information extraction, and subject/topic modelling is created to evaluate Amazon data sets such as (Rating, Product Type, Price, Time interval, and Quantity Sold).
6. **Chapter – 6**, depicts an effective model, which utilizes the Software-Defined Networking (SDN) in collaboration with blockchain with versatile implementation. In this chapter, the major objective of our research is to optimize the security between various E-commerce applications/business, also to mitigate the single point failure of security vulnerabilities via Blockchain-based SDN

framework. Our proposed model also utilises the trust between E-commerce applications with the help of blockchain-based trust key distribution.

7. **Chapter – 7**, provides the summary of overall contributions of the proposed research in term of trust evaluation, trust is investigated based on (similarity between the new transaction and the past transactions), (user’s feedback analysis and mining), and SDN based blockchain trust evaluation. In this chapter, future research directions are also discussed.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

2.1 Motivation

In this chapter, the idea of trust is critically presented in the subsequent chapter with the help of a detailed existing literature survey. Depending on a review of the literature, it provides an outline of the various conceptual framework of trust and addresses the feasible meaning of trust. More explicitly, this section will concentrate on E-commerce trust and the methodologies to develop it.

2.2 Overview of Existing Research Gaps and Motivation

Our proposed research mainly focused to deal with existing issues and research gaps such as Single-point failure, centralization issues, how to handle big data with a cache system, and machine learning to evaluate trust, In addition to this our research also focused on credential information such as user privacy. In existing research, most of the authors have failed to properly evaluate and provide a reliable

trust model in terms of user privacy, single-point failure, and larger data handling techniques.

Single-point failure issues - Most of the existing work specially blockchain-based trust evaluation models and trust models with security approaches they mainly focused on single-point security and trust evaluation approaches, during the failure of such a single point, the entire model can lead towards severe damage. Centralization - Many attacking vector classification approaches are based on a centralized paradigm in which an attacker is categorized by a centralized cloud server running an intrusion detection system [39]. These approaches are difficult to handle since the entire infrastructure involves a big number of users.

Big data problem - Large amounts of data are collected from communication equipment and real-time data processing systems, making spotting security risks a difficult task in big data environments. Multiple data sets enable particular decisions to be made in real-time so that actions may be taken accordingly. In contrast, extracting and analysing real-time data from E-commerce platforms would be prohibitively expensive.

Lack of privacy- Data security is not a priority in the most current threat detection technologies. They process data in several ways without the owner's permission. Furthermore, due to the issue of user privacy, it is difficult to obtain enough data for current techniques of identifying attacks, resulting in erroneous identification predictions.

2.3 Trust and Reputation Overview

According to authors of [23], the trust in E-commerce can be defined in several ways based on the type of nature such as based on trust context and sensitivity, the trust can be manipulated or change with time and environment. For example, a buyer

might purchase products from an unknown online seller followed by the displayed history and previous transaction records. Typically, the buyer will purchase from a seller who has positive feedback in his/her past transactions history. However, other buyers might take a risk and go with the better bargain despite lower or no ratings. This possibility just shows the subjectivity of trust.

Its multi-disciplinary nature is another interesting aspect of trust, as demonstrated by the ways in which the subject has been discussed by researchers from vastly different disciplines including history, sociology, economics, and philosophy as well computer science. With the appearance of online trading sources such as Amazon and eBay and social networks such as Facebook, the issue of trustworthiness evaluation requires not just knowledge of mathematics and computing, but also a sociological and behavioural approach. Because of its many facts and meanings in different contexts, trust is an excellent subject for multi-disciplinary, socio-technological research [101].

In the social sciences, scholars and practitioners have acknowledged organizational behaviour and conflict resolution and taken these as tools to recognise cooperative endeavours. However, the literature also suggests that the elaboration of theoretical frameworks has been hindered because trust is not significantly used as the main topic with sociology. According to [30], the sociological perspective views trust, thus the social sciences' view of trust is very much in line with that online business scenario as both of proposed solutions are capable to deal with collective users behaviours. According to E-commerce online framework, trust is not manipulated with only preferences of individuals but instead through collective interactions. As a result, sociological theories such as Social Capital Theory can also be used to establish a physical model for the effectiveness of increased ties and structures on trust [160].

Trust became more critical and central over periods of uncertainty due to orga-

nizational crisis, demonstrating its practical use in online business settings when facing risks and uncertainties. According to [104], the Compact Oxford English dictionary emphasizes the belief aspect of trust, defining the term as a “firm belief in the reliability, truth, ability, or strength of someone or something”.

The author in [149] defined trust from the aspect of risk, stating that “(a) an individual is confronted with an ambiguous path, a path that can lead to an event perceived to be beneficial or to an event perceived to be harmful; (b) he perceives that the occurrence of these events is contingent on the behaviour of another person; and (c) he perceives the strength of a harmful event to be greater than the strength of a beneficial event. If he chooses to take an ambiguous path with such properties, he makes a trusting choice; else he makes a distrustful choice.” The author in [60] defined trust based on subjectivity probability, contending that trust is “the subjective probability by which an individual, A, expects that another individual, B, performs a given action on which its welfare depends.”

The author in [149] has defined trust from transitivity relationship, giving the following conditions: IF A trusts B and B trusts C, THEN A will Trust C (depending on the hypothesis, which A is told to trust C by B). This is called a recommendation. The author in [36] defined trust from a composition of multiple attributes as “the firm belief in the competence of an entity to act dependably, securely, and reliably within the specified context.”

It is mainly emerged as one of the most common components of online marketing, to seek coordination among strongly correlated and geographically distributed agents. Amazon, eBay, Yahoo auction, and other similar business sites use simple trust management frameworks in order to provide their users with information about the companies’ trust. Given the success of these environments, trust mechanisms can be considered as a feasible solution to collect and evaluate the trust factor in collaboration with each other interaction. There is also the need for a stronger

system. According to [123], Reputation was described by the Compact Oxford Dictionary as a type of confidence, In which the trust is stated as “the belief or opinions that are generally held about someone or something”. It is worth noting that reputaion is a trust-related term but has an entirely different interpretation, such that the concepts could be used despite overlapping them.

The authors of [71] defined trust as “an expectation about an agent’s behaviour based on information about or observations of its past behaviour.” According to [8], this definition means that the trust of any entity is considered a reliable collective measure of trustworthiness based on the history of that entity’s interactions with and recommendations from other members of the surrounding community. trust is one of the most important concepts of a community, and it is used to monitor community members by using certain techniques to show the chance of positive or negative interactions – thus predicting the likelihood of successful or unsuccessful interactions in the future. Therefore, trust is an effective tool that helps to make community members make informed decisions. To enable this process, then, a trust system needs to gather certain pieces of required information, including personal experiences and recommendations from members, in order to be a successful system.

2.4 Trust and Reputation Management in Distributed Systems

According to [126], there is a noticeable growth in reputation mechanisms within platforms and applications such as online marketing, multi-agent environments, social networks, mobile ad-hoc networks, and peer-to-peer networks. It is also worth mentioning that much research has been conducted to design models for trust and reputation management within these environments. An effective design of trust and reputation management models can decrease the risk and can guarantee a network’s

competitiveness.

2.4.1 Overview of E-commerce

This section focuses on studies on trust and reputation countermeasures for E-commerce and E-commerce platforms in general. In recent decades, E-commerce has expanded and been a part of the everyday lives of global customers. As per [140], E-commerce is described as internet and electronic system that provides an online infrastructure and enables buyers and sellers to share information, complete purchases and handle other transactions. It should also be noted that E-commerce comprises the 3 separate categories mentioned below:

1. Business to Customer (B2C)
2. Business to Business (B2B)
3. Consumer to Consumer (C2C)

With the growth of E-commerce, trust and reputation management have become real sources of concern for platforms, particularly regarding monetary transactions. Issues of trust, such as worries about payment method theft or insufficient reputation information, can increase both the buyer's and the seller's hesitation to conduct transactions if there is a higher probability of problems with a transaction. Uncertainty or confidence thus translate directly into impacts on efficiency, profit, and the entire electronic market. Many researchers have introduced elements of trust and reputation systems into E-commerce, which evaluate users on every completed transaction [166]. Constructing a central framework with a history of credit scores, such as, is one probable solution for dealing with user reputations, but an approach like this cannot always take standards and individual preferences into consideration.

E-marketplaces and shopping sites such as Amazon, eBay, and On Sale Exchange use simple online trust mechanisms in order to avoid cheating or frauds. In Amazon, every seller and buyer are rated after every transaction, so a new user has no trust value. The value of the trust score is calculated as the aggregate value of all feedback scores from the very first record of history. eBay uses 1, 0, or -1 as a trustworthiness value to rate sellers after every transaction and then computes the average of seller trust score of all acquired rating within six months transaction. While the new user has 0 as a trust value. In On Sale, the buyers can submit textual comments in order to rate the sellers. The overall trust of a seller is an average of his/her customers' ratings, so again a new seller on On sale has no trust.

However, one common problem evident with all three of these systems is that they depend on users' cooperation in actually rating and giving their opinions on sellers they have interacted with. Another common problem is that users can easily create new identities and discard poorly-rated ones. eBay and Amazon have tried to resolve at least the second problem by requiring every new user to register with his/her valuable information, which provides support to track and trace the real-time status.

Zhu et al [169] proposed the trust mechanism for electronic users, the proposed model utilises the ranges within the range of 0.3000 with 0, such values are used to assign new users. The system was designed to accept only the most recent ratings in order to avoid the issue of two users deliberately increasing their trust value through repeated interaction. In Sporas, more weight is assigned to the latest ratings in order to evaluate user trust since these latest ratings are much closer to their present behaviour. Sporas is similar to credit score systems in that users have low scores when they begin to use the system, and their scores will improve as they continue to perform and meet goals over time. In Sporas, the low starting score does not affect the user's assigned trust value, but one of the system's most considerable disadvantages is that the starting trust value of 0 takes a long time to

be increased.

The authors in [134] proposed a comparable mechanism for e-markets, which examines the trust role between seller and buyer, the influence of feedback such as positive or negative, also the importance of risk factors in trust formation. They drew data from an online auction market and an online experiment and then analysed it to show that credibility-based trust is one of the most important predictors of economic outcomes: trust can lead to higher prices. The authors in [23] proposed a distributed trust framework called “DIRECT” to help prevent dishonesty in web-based applications and E-commerce. DIRECT uses statistical distributed techniques to monitor and detect the malicious attacks of dishonest nodes. Mainly capable to interpret the various issues of feedback with dishonest feedback, such approach is used to divide feed-backs into two categories (RED and GREEN), where model only keeps the record the trust based history, which is considered as green in proposed work. The proposed model is used to actively reduce the amount and effects of dishonest feedback.

The authors in [104] proposed a trust model called “TRUNITS,” which is based on the aggregation of trust units and can secure buyers from malicious sellers in e-marketplaces. TRUNITS requires a sufficient number of trust units per seller before completing a transaction and also displays a score of all obtained trust units from all past buyers. A seller must have a sufficient quantity of trust units before being able to complete a transaction. If the buyer is satisfied after the transaction, the seller will gain more units; otherwise, the seller will lose units. An interesting trend is obvious in the literature discussed above: for the most part, trustworthiness is modelled on feedback ratings or trust, which involves only a single scalar value. However, others focused on trust and reputation systems from the fraud side – also effective, but again only a single scalar value. Voiding frauds by an automatic frauds detection can play an important role in enhancing the efficiency of e-marketplaces. The authors in [122] focused on identifying and evaluating the main features that

can display the evidence of fraud in an e-marketplace's trust systems, and then described some procedures that can extract these features. The analyses of their study were based on the features of the user and the procedures of the negotiation between sellers and buyers. They also studied and quantified the influence of each feature in both behaviours (fraudulent and normal) in a real-world dataset. They believed that any trust system can benefit from a mechanism that enables it to detect frauds and improve credibility.

2.4.2 E-commerce Types

Nowadays, E-commerce industries are exponentially growing due to diversified nature, it has been used worldwide for several reasons. Business information systems are one area, for particular, services that sell acquired consumer information to anyone else for commercial reasons. Publicity can also be identified on blogs and internet sites [46]. E-commerce can be categorised in various directions.

There are two forms of E-commerce listed in the book such as indirect E-commerce and direct E-commerce. The E-commerce with the indirect approach is used for consumers who wish to place orders at distant locations, make payment with online invoices or cash on delivery time, where products are consumed with old fashion.

On the other side E-commerce based on a direct approach, is where customers buy, paying, and also get a digitized item, such as software, music, and web applications. There have been various forms of primary and indirect E-commerce. Major forms of E-commerce, which are widely used comprise on Business-to-Business (B2B), Business-to-Consumer (B2C), Consumer-to-Business) (C2B), Consumer-to-Consumer (C2C), Business-to-Government (B2G) and Mcommerce (WikiBooks, 2006) [1].

E-commerce vendors are businesses and associations which provide electronic busi-

ness platforms and goods. As per [14], which is considered as a mandatory and feasible factor in E-commerce industries, which are provided as below:

1. **Reliability** - The payment and electronic payment company are used to expand the credit, increase the security, and resolve the bill. The same efficiency is demanded of the supplier of E-commerce services.
2. **Security** - Security concerns can never vanish entirely, so the security provider should strive to identify potential vulnerabilities and establish new security options for others.
3. **Simplicity** - Computerized trading systems are effective when they are easy, uncomplicated, and cheaper than trading in person.
4. **Acceptability** - Electronic commerce strategies can provide universal public acceptance.

2.4.3 Pros and Cons of E-commerce

E-commerce keeps expanding and customers are shopping over the internet for several facts although, authors of [58] have provided the four primary reasons given as below: Convenience – Any consumer can place an order whatever they wanted with no physical activities such as going away from home to get products.

- Greater supply - Any consumer is capable to several products lists, categories on the online market, as in physical market they cannot perceive such varieties in a typical market because online retailers can reduce their stock by close coordination with distributors.
- Lower prices - Internet retailers can reduce their prices. For instance, storage costs may be lowered, allowing customers to provide lower rates.

- Price comparison - Customers can measure the costs of suppliers for goods and services. Potential customers may either do this on their own or with the aid of an electronic agent, such as Cost Runner, who calculates everyone.

Besides, [128] point out that potential explanations for internet shopping are that it makes life easier and also because customers are more empowered due to various improved quality knowledge and because of the opportunity to consider alternative retailer offers. Though there are still certain unfavourable sides of online shopping. There seems to be an example, that certain items are not suitable for internet sales and that many customers enjoy the actual buying experience of feeling stuff and trying things on. Another negative thing is the issues with replacement goods which do not satisfy the specifications of the customer. Often if consumers are not satisfied with trust factors and business brands, these are unwilling to engage in the internet market to place online order. Because the actual environment of purchasing in a conventional firm lacks the trust and E-commerce factors, the question of confidence is becoming a big problem for many shoppers, addition to this, there is lack of justification for buyers with trust to place order online.

2.4.4 Multi-Agent Environments

In recent years, multi-agent approaches have gradually become one of the most common solutions for different applications (E-commerce, product life cycle management, supply chain management, etc.) to deal with trust and trustworthiness. “One source of data to build a trust management system which is to collect and save referrals from other agents” [85]. To deal with referrals between agents, they developed a model in which A as the agent assigns a trust rating to B depending on three types of evidence:

1. A’s direct observations of B

2. B's ratings given by its neighbours
3. A's ratings of these neighbours

The second aspect of their model is to collect trust data among the different agents and compile a social approach. However, this model does not consider the existence and interference of malicious agents, which can distort trust data to achieve their own goals. The author in [123] developed a mechanism that can help agents to cope in selfish environments as well as with other cooperative agents. They represented their simulation scenario to an E-commerce environment to show the practical problem and solution. They also discussed the technique used to gather information from the community as well as trust-related issues of transitivity.

In [85], authors have presented trust model with open multi-agents approach, which incorporates interaction-based and role-based trust along with trust witness to initiate trust metric. Their model is to help agents to gain advantages rather than a set of benchmarks. They also introduced the main concept of certified trust, which means that the third party reference. Their model "FIRE" is considered a flexible system since it can respond to the environmental changes in the society of agents. The author in [85] developed a probabilistic model for the environment of multi-agents as a virtual firm where the agents need to interact with strangers.

2.4.5 Networks with Peer to Peer (P2P) Approach

P2P networks are distributed in nature, most of them are not capable to use the centralised approach for maintenance. Communication amongst peers can be explicitly accomplished, thus increasing the chances of a buyer or seller interacting with anonymous entities whose trustworthiness is unknown. These kinds of systems need a trust management system in order to assure inter-peer cooperation and control the effects of misbehaving entities [4]. Peers can only protect them-

selves by their ability to recognize trustworthy peers for communication and this is one of the main challenges in P2P networks. Because of this, trust management and reputation systems are a critical part of securing large-scale P2P networks. There are many trust and reputation systems that have been shown to encourage honest peer-to-peer interaction by incentivising cooperating and punishing misbehaviour. According to [37], the use of trust and reputation systems helps decrease malicious transactions in P2P networks by filtering out misbehaving peers.

The authors in [1] proposed a protocol called P.Grid, which utilises the decentralised approach. In P-Grid, malicious peers are identified by complaint-based systems. However, P-Grid can only show negative feedback. Therefore a trusted peer cannot be separated from an untested candidate. In the course of evaluating trust, peers are graded on a conditional basis as trusted or dishonest; which quickly proves insufficient. Furthermore, in this protocol, trust is measured by only recommendations from neighbourhoods and is not dependent on global knowledge.

Another protocol called TrustMe was proposed by [38] as a means of accessing and maintaining the information of trust ratings in P2P networks. It utilises the several random activities of Trust-Holding Agent peers (THA) via public key cryptography process to provide the secure and reliable feature and to avoid the anonymity or resist several attacks. Most of the peers use messages to propagate their ratings of others and reports to broadcast their feedback. However, this system requires a tremendous number of messages to be created, and it takes a very long time to transmit information and build a trust.

EigenTrust[39] was suggested as a credibility technique to reduce the number of in-authentic file-sharing downloads on the P2P file-sharing platform. EidenTrust gives the importance of global trust dependent on the uploading background of each peer in the group. Where a secure and distributed model uses power iteration to evaluate the trust values globally. Peers can select the peers from whom they download

using the global trust value in this algorithm. In their simulations, the authors showed how malicious peers could be identified and removed from the network by this kind of trust system. However, this system also lacks anonymity because the algorithm uses IP addresses to identify peers. It also places massive overheads on network resources with its consumption of huge network bandwidth.

The authors in [40] proposed a trust system called PeerTrust, this promotes the use of an integrated confidence framework to assess and correlate the truthfulness of subordinates. In this system, a peer's trustworthiness is computed based on three parameters taken from trust and two taken as adaptive factors. The three factors are input from other participants, the cumulative amount of peer payments, and the reliability of providing feedback. The variables, on the other hand, are the background of the purchase and the application environment. The specific confidence metric is determined by integrating certain variables.

The Peer Trust framework modifies to the actions of multiple peers and uses customised comparisons to assess the integrity of peers. It also indicates the importance of identifying parameters of trust as well as the adaptive factors, and it even addresses the problem of dishonest feedback. The main issue with the PeerTrust model is that it is difficult to implement and use within a large-scale P2P network. PowerTrust is another trust system proposed by the authors in [41]. This framework operates by using a trust overlay network (TON) to simulate confidence and explore input interactions between partners in massive Network systems. After analysing more than 10,000 interaction results in eBay, the investigators found that consumers wanted a power-law that was communicated through user input. PowerTrust was developed in response to this need by leveraging the power-law distribution of peer feedback. This model chooses the trustworthy power node with the aggregation of total system records. However, this system is disadvantaged by the way it cannot account for peer selfishness or collusion.

FuzzyTrust is a P2P trust system proposed by the authors in [42] based on fuzzy logic. FuzzyTrust is utilised for manipulating fuzziness, uncertainty, and lack of information in the reports on peer trust. Peer trusts are aggregated with a responsible message overhead in this system. Each peer record contains two tables, which are the transaction record, maintaining account information with distant peers and local records (maintaining remote peers' ratings of valued trust. The Distributed-hash-table in this system is used to perform rapid and safe trust propagation among peers. After comparing FuzzyTrust and EigenTrust, the authors showed that FuzzyTrust was able to detect more malicious peers within four iterations, and also operated slightly faster than EigenTrust. However, the FuzzyTrust system lacked any specific techniques to tackle misbehaving peers, which is a significant disadvantage.

VCG is a reward trust mechanism proposed by the authors in [37] and is used to encourage peers to give honest feedback. It is designed based on the social feature of trust networks as well as well-known economic models. In this system, trust feedback is considered as a specific category of information, and peers are encouraged to give honest feedback about each other. Considering the subjective nature of principles of trust and reputation, the authors classified trust into two types: functional trust and referral trust. Referral trust is also extended to contain two factors in order to reduce the errors of trust inference. These two factors are Similarity (to differentiate the personal trust feedback) and Truthfulness (to evaluate the credibility of trust feedback). The result of their simulation shows how such proposals and the existence of certain properties benefit the P2P network. Besides the incentives concept, [43] also consider options for punishment. They extended the trust system to motivate good behaviour and discourage maliciousness among peers. They considered punishment and incentives as opposite but complementary functions that can cope with reliable and malicious peers. Those who used the Game-Theoretic methodology to develop a trustworthy economic structure for Network systems.

2.4.6 Social Networks

The noticeable growth of social networks, social media sites, and other sources of online sharing information means that potential users also need good online constructions in order to enjoy greater access[44]. There are many studies on social networks to this end, and these networks are recognized as one of the interesting areas for some researchers to the model given how their users utilize the social networks' own frameworks to interact with others. According to [45], the analysis of social networks can be processed into methods groups to evaluate the analyse the relational characteristics of these structures. With the existence of malicious users and the possibility of lying, cheating, and distributing false information, trust is crucial to keeping social networks secured and users able to evaluate one another's trustworthiness.

The Social Trust system was introduced to demonstrate the importance of designing a convenient trust model from a sociological point of view, and to prove how important it is to identify users' trustworthiness and establish trust as a descriptor in well description form and to provide the encryption. Social confidence is recommended for social reasons, including integrity, privacy, friendships, and a degree of social trust as users are involved in both direct and indirect interactions. Tidal-trust is a trust metric proposed by the authors in [46] which can be used for either friend-of-a-friend networks or semantic webs. In this system, every node is assigned a local trust value, which can be used to show the levels of trust among two nodes that have not interacted yet. The trust algorithm's process is based on the recommendations provided by strongly trusted nodes and through shorter paths that might provide more accurate information. However, this algorithm lacks the ability to update the values of trust. In addition, it does not consider observations based on direct experience.

A gravity-based model is proposed by the authors in [47] using the trust to manage

the activities in the social networks. In this model, there have been two stages for each consumer. The very first stage is a relationship, in which the attributes of the user are computed within the sense of a trustworthy mutual neighbourhood. The second phase is the advanced program of trust for user groups who are not even interacting and are calculated using social neighbours. STrust is another social trust model proposed by the authors in [48], which is used by social networks in order to build a community using both social capital and recommendation systems. This system is derived from social capital and divides all interactions within a social network into two groups: popularity and engagement. Each of these two groups provides different things within the social network and captures inactive interactions like reading comments without giving feedback. The values of each group are computed by deriving metrics from the social capital and both are based on a member's trustworthiness in the community.

The authors in [49] introduced social access control (SAC) for protecting social data. They used a trust model to assign each subject and object on the social network its own level of trust. In this structure, the trustworthiness of the particular topic is calculated as the average of the trust ratings provided by the community, while the originator recognises the trust level of the object. The measurement of an object class is governed by the use of the connected trust values of subjectivity and objectivity. In contrast, this platform provides the trust of read-only-data items.

2.4.7 The Mobile Ad-Hoc Network (MANET)

Mobile Ad Hoc Networks (MANETs) are defined as group mobile nodes, which work wireless and communicate with each other without a centralized administration or fixed networks infrastructures. Therefore, MANETs is infrastructure fewer networks which means that every node cooperates in order to provide the network functionality. According to [50] the characteristics of MANETs –which include re-

peated changes, the topology of the network because of mobility, open wireless operation nodes, these can make these nodes more vulnerable to security issues if a cooperative and friendly environment cannot be presumed. As a result, many trusts and reputation models have been evaluated as options to increase such networks' security and encourage nodes to evaluate their neighbours' behaviours. This section comprises a literature review of some important issues regarding evaluating trustworthiness in MANETs. The authors in [51] proposed the CORE model. Elements of this framework are accompanied by a smart contract that can distinguish among both three types of data: qualitative credibility, indirect trust, and functional trust. In this system, only positive recommendations are accepted. Therefore, the CORE model's effectiveness can be reduced since nodes cannot exchange information about bad experiences.

The authors in [52] proposed a mechanism called Context-Aware Detection, which is used to link the accusations of nodes to a path discovery process and a particular period of time. This approach can detect many kinds of attacks and attackers and dismiss invalid rout information at an early stage. CONFIDANT is another mechanism proposed by the authors in [53] to detect and remove malicious nodes using recommendations and observations. It deals with the issue of dishonest recommendations through personal experiences. It also tests the recommendations received from nodes by a deviation test and blocks any recommendation with a deviation value greater than the threshold value. Therefore, the system updates the trust value of recommending nodes based on the deviation test results. There is another model proposed by the authors in [54] that can support nodes to cooperate with the help of direct observations and suggestions. Only the last viewpoint sent by a node to the credibility manger framework is acknowledged in this framework. While it is always up to date on trustworthiness, then, this model is not enough in order to recognise the node's overall behaviour.

RFSTrust is a trust model based on fuzzy recommendations, similar to the one

proposed by the authors in [55]. It is also used to evaluate the trustworthiness of node using similarity theory. RFSTrust examines and evaluates the relationships of recommendation between nodes and if the degree of similarity is high, then the consistency in the evaluation will be increased. The authors in [56] proposed a Recommendation Exchange Protocol (REP) to permit a node to communicate with neighbours by sending and receiving recommendations based on how long the nodes have known each other. In this system, the long-term associated recommendations have more weight than the short-term associated recommendations.

The authors in [11] introduce a mobile ad hoc structural function of a credibility trust evaluation model. A game is predicated trust evaluation framework that qualifies users' comments based on previous relationships between both the Sender and Recipient base station. The model's utility was shown by the system's capability to improve communication between nodes by lowering packet drop ratios and maximizing benefit.

The authors in [3] proposed a trust-based routing mechanism called (TRUNCMAN) to remove non-collaborative nodes, using route discovery processes to defend against attackers. This protocol is divided into two phases, which are the detection phase (used to detect non-collaborative nodes) and the suspicion phase (used to check the requested broadcast and acknowledgement). However, this system does not consider the dynamic characteristics of MANETs, the quality of routes, and the attributes of social networks, which are distinct disadvantages. The authors in [119] suggest a recommended confidence model that uses a clustering strategy to automatically filter attacks linked to unethical suggestions, based on amount of connections, knowledge reliability and the proximity to the nodes, over a certain period of time.

The authors in [119] suggest a recommendation-based confidence model with a defensive scheme that uses a clustering strategy to systematically root off attacks rel-

evant to deceptive recommendations over time-based on the number of connections, knowledge compatibility, and node proximity. The model is empirically evaluated in a variety of mobile and isolated topologies in which nodes are subjected to changes in their immediate surroundings, resulting in periodic route changes. In a complex MANET environment, the empirical study shows the trust model's robustness and accuracy.

2.5 Different Level of Trust Evaluation in E-commerce

2.5.1 Trust Evaluation on Infrastructure level

At this level, the trust management system is more focused on the reliability of information than the content. Initially, trust management systems used security policies to establish trust, since they were applied for security purposes and prioritized reliability of information[57]. Therefore, traditional security techniques such as encryption, authentication, and access control could be adopted. Kerberos designed a protocol taking advantage of a third party to ease the interchange of digital signature between a user and computer. Keynote in [59] and PolicyMaker in [60] use the authentication of signature to shape the relationship of trust between a trustor and a trustee.

2.5.2 Trust Evaluation on Service level

At this level, trust management systems are more focused on evaluating information content, which can indicate the interaction between a trustor and trustee or between direct and indirect experiences. In an open E-commerce environment where users (suppliers and consumers) easily access and interact with information, the evaluation of security-oriented trust leads to a huge overhead of trust manage-

ment systems[61]. Here instead then, the establishment of trust between members is based on the set of the information that members have maintained about one another.

2.5.3 Trust Evaluation on Community Level

There are many intersections between socially-oriented and service-oriented trust management in term of components. Thus, a new problem with regard to trust information relationship is the social environment in which it has come up. In general, trust management at this level involves modelling the relationship between members in environments where the relationships might be affected by psychology, social science, or philosophy[57]. More precisely, within a large-social network, the path of trust will be expanded to include more members, and thus the trust information relationship (e.g. trust information propagation) becomes more complex and can be affected by social or personal factors[62].

2.5.4 Trust Evaluation with and without Contextual Information

In the literature, there are some models of trust evaluation have been considered in some applications. In this section, we divided the trust evaluation models into two groups according to their relationships with the context information.

Most of the existing trust evaluation models are proposed in several applications for example in P2P networks. The general value of a peer is calculated by aggregating the binary trust ratings(0,1) [66]. These models [87], [158], [152], [86] do not consider the contextual information and only focus on a signal or final trust level to show the general trust status of a seller. As a result, the buyer might not be able to know how the seller has obtained this high value of trust, which makes it difficult

to predict the success for completing the forthcoming transactions in a trustworthy environment.

On the other hand, there are some models taking into account the relationship between the evaluation of trust and context information.

2.5.5 Multi-Dimensional Trust Evaluation models

Griffiths in [45] proposes Multi-Dimensional Trust Model (MDT) which is based on Marsh's general trust model. However, MDT is slightly different because the author takes into the accounts some attributes of the transaction such as time, quality and cost and a buyer can specify the weight of the attributes for trust computation. In these models, the buyers evaluate the sellers based on their own direct experiences. The author mentioned that MDT can be considered as a complementary to "general trust" as the buyers can get the trust value of a seller in a specific situation from a different dimension, for example, the trust value of a seller can be trustworthy in selling cars from different dimensions such as time to handle the transaction and the quality of cars but the buyer might not be sure about the trust of the seller if she/he sells something else. Therefore, MDT is not able to prevent the value imbalance problem.

In [113] proposes REGRET system, which is used to enhance the calculation of trust and reputation values. This system uses a framework called SuppWorld in order to test the complicated models. REGRET system is similar to MDT, the trust and reputation values of sellers are evaluated from different dimensions and buyers can weight these dimensions by their own experiences and general trust.

2.5.6 Contextual Inheritance Trust Evaluation Models (CI)

Strang et al. [131] mentioned that "ontologies are considered as a promising instrument to specify concepts and interrelations". Consequently, many researchers have used the ontology as a structure in order to analysis the awareness of context trust. Uschold et al. in [144] explained the related ontology conception. Generally, although, the ontology is a conceptual model, it also can explain the relationship between different concepts. These relationships could be either *a kind of* referred to inheritance, *a part of* referred to part and overall and *an instance of*.

Some studies deal with the issues of contextual evaluation by focusing on the main conception of the inherited trust. The authors [54] mentioned that context can be hierarchically structured. For instance, if I trust my brother to drive me to the airport, so I can give him my car's keys. Then 'giving him my car's keys' is considered a subset of the access rights of driving my car. In [115] the authors propose a hierarchical model of trust in contexts (HMTC) which can be used to discover the relations between contexts. The authors believe that in order to deduce the trust value from one context to another, there is a need to identify hierarchical structures between contexts. Thus their model differs from ours because in contextual properties such as amount category, a hierarchy is a tree structure and we have considered the number of transactions that falls in a certain range as been discussed in the methodology section

2.5.7 Contextual Similarity Trust Evaluation Models

Mui in [91] summarised the description of context-based trust evaluation in the following example. *A* who has not been in interaction with *B*. *A* asks other parties in the same context what they rate *B* (before being in any interaction with *B*). If the weighted sum of the rating from other parties is bigger than the certain

threshold, the trust between A and B will be established. However, in order to evaluate the forthcoming transaction, the buyer depends on the others' ratings (who have been in a transaction with the same seller before) and then compare context similarity between two buyers. [131] compared between different approaches to model context and based on their comparison, they believe that key value-based model is not effective to describe the complexity in the relationship within the context. For example, Digital projector and Inkjet network printer are not the same products but they both have similarity because both are types of computer output devices. For this reason, buyers may trust the seller and buy the provided printer because they know this seller has a good trust for selling a good quality digital projector. They also believe that ontology is a good instrument to identify concepts and interrelations [143] propose Context-Aware Trust model (CAT) which is used to compare the context similarity by using key values, which can describe a certain context to some extent for an open and dynamic system. They introduce a parameter of context-similarity.

2.5.8 Feedback Comment Analysis

Most research on the study of reviews in E-commerce applications [97], [82], [42], [52]. [97] and [82] depend on the sentimental analysis of reviews. Feedback responses have been found to be disruptive and so interpreting these would be a challenging task. The absent aspect comments in [97] are assumed to be negative and the prototypes constructed from aspect scores are used to identify comments as positively or negatively. The [52] methodology for summarising input comments is introduced with the intention of filtering out courteous feedback that does not have an honest opinion. The goal of [82] is to produce "ranked aspect overview" from feedback comments from eBay. Their predictive conceptual model is based on a downturn in average transaction rankings.

The authors in [12] considered a possible change to an eBay-style reputation model, with their interest in seeing how approachability and the demographic of users would grow if the intensity of the comments/feedback was allocated based on previous interaction between participants. They categorize information sources into various categories to determine an aggregation approach for reputability evaluation that takes into account adding a continuously determined weight to and source of comments.

2.5.9 Extraction of Aspect Opinion

The main aim of our research is associated with the information extraction and sentiment-based evaluation of free text-based comments records. Based on this topic, a detailed description and analysis of the approach are also discussed in the existing work of [146] and [79]. The authors of [55], [103] and [170] has also carried out research for mining aspect opinion especially on product ratings and movie reviews. Frequent nouns and function words in [55] are called facts of product feedback, and an opinion lexicon is created for the purpose of defining opinions. This is further suggested in [103] to add lexical information patterns to enhance the precision of the extraction dimension. Dependence interaction filtering is used in [170] for the movie reviews based aspect opinion. Nevertheless, most of these researchers have not pragmatically evaluated and organised these opinions according to opinions phases or opinions groups.

Several aspects opinion of some workgroups are provided in clustered, implying [163] is provided to individual opinion statements. Recently, a semi-supervised [92] technique was introduced for extracting aspects and grouping them into coherent classes, under the supervision of input from the user item sets. Unsupervised subject modelling algorithms have been employed to collectively construct views and aspects (or topics) centred either on the probabilistic Latent Semantic Analysis

(PLSA) [53] or the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) [13]. Theories differ in granularities [88], [76], [15] and also how aspects and views communicate with [88], [76], [15], [167]. After all, each of these current works is dependent on a uni-gram of the interpretation of texts, and almost none of them allow the use of any lexical information.

In the E-commerce input comments or recommendations [82], [55] and [55], there has been some latest analysis on computation aspect scores from general scores. Based on the correlation of overall ratings, their feature ratings and weights are evaluated but significant positive bias is not reflected in the overall ratings. As E-commerce industries has been exponentially increasing towards online market with rapid growth. As E-commerce commercially adopted but there are several cyber-attacks and other fraudulent activities also rising due to rapid growth. To overcome such issues, block chain is significantly use in various E-commerce applications.

2.6 The BlockChain (BC) Main Features

1. **Decentralised feature-** Data exchanges (i.e., money transfers) in centralized communication networks are evaluated and authorized by several third parties' entities with trust assessment approach. This also results in higher costs due to the fact of decentralisation management and several repairs and maintenance. In BC infrastructure, mainly two separate nodes also support to interact with transactions with one another with no trigger of trust to believe an enabled system to maintain count or to carry out permission.
2. **Immutability** - In immutability feature, manipulating with BC is far more complex, it is vulnerable to censorship although all new modules produced in the BC are determined by peers through decentralised consensus. In reality, all currently kept a record in the BC are still permanent, and an intruder will need to breach much of the nodes participating in the BC network to modify

the previous records. Therefore, any modifications are quickly detected in the BC information.

3. **Audit-ability** - Both stakeholders possess a BC copy, and can therefore access all transaction records labelled with timestamps. This openness enables peers to try looking up purchases containing individual BC addresses and check them. Since BC attributes are not correlated with names in everyday life, this offers a form of pseudo-anonymity. While BC record repository account is not capable to track the original users, it is also possible to keep individual BC addresses responsible and to draw inferences about transactions which are generated by only single BC address.
4. **Fault-Tolerance Feature** - Many of the BC peers have the same replicas of the records in the database. Via central advantages, any weaknesses or extrapolations that occur in the BC context can be discovered and information leakages can be minimised later through using replicas contained in BC peer.

2.7 Blockchain main Building Blocks

1. **Transaction** - Authorized bits of information, initially generated by the broadcaster's network parties, then distributed to the entire framework. Payments are validated and checked using encryption primitives before they are hashed and incorporated in a Merkle tree whose origin or root is considered as the hash of node [89].
2. **Blocks** - These are lists of purchases that instead of being authenticated are added to the BC. Through block includes a timeframe, a unique ID also called the Merkle tree hash values, and a parent block ID that acts as a connection among them.
3. **Distributed Ledger** - This includes all the blocks generated that build

up the system. First, legitimate transactions are attached to the current blockchain, then synchronized and eventually transmitted over the internet. Consequently, any network device will have the same repository replica.

4. **Hashing mechanism/Public keys** - Connecting the various blocks in a series. BC is, by default, intrinsically immune to the alteration of results. Information in any specific frame should not be wrongfully modified until registered, since this will legitimize all databases in the preceding BC blocks [38].

2.8 Overview of Blockchain Applications in E-commerce

There have been numerous previous types of research that recommend applying blockchain technologies to E-commerce payment systems [24] or suggesting frameworks for application consumers to obtain trust scores [20, 117]. For example, in 2015, Carboni launched a decentralised input management framework developed on the base of the Bitcoin blockchain through altering the current Bitcoin protocol [20][18]. Nonetheless, this model has a possible susceptibility to information to obtain, which may be accomplished by purposefully providing exceptionally high or low ratings to unauthorised users. The author suggested that perhaps the concern could be alleviated by obtaining feedback from the parties to payment (i.e. pass money). In 2016, Schaub et al. proposed a trustless trust framework based on blockchain which anonymizes the client identity [117]. Both assessment details are conveniently placed in the blocks, and the framework allows users to assess one another without caring about retribution. But this strategy will cause unexpected consequences in everyday reality. In anonymously operated Web communities, for example, users may discredit others without any legitimate reason. As a

consequence, the anticipated benefit of utilising anonymity may be deterred due to inaccurate data produced on the network.

PeerTrust [157] suggested a cohesive concept of adaptive confidence to measure and evaluate peers' trustworthiness, focused on a transaction-driven input mechanism close to ours. The suggested approach integrates three simple factors and two adaptive confidence factors in measuring mutual trustworthiness, the payment background component and group background component. Building trust and credibility designs acceptable for the specific application is not even an easy process, but in most cases, it is also not possible to know the internal operations of a commercial system.

Resnick et al. [109] evaluated the eBay credibility program, including some of the oldest and best-known E-commerce credibility schemes on the Website, that for each purchase collects feedback from producers and consumers on each other. The research describes some important aspects from either the 1999 review of a big data sample. There is just no ability to determine eBay's internal processes, nevertheless, the research has not really introduced a modified model. Siau and Shen's work [127] concluded that increasing consumer trust is a dynamic process involving technologies and market practises, as well as going from preliminary self-improvement to continuous trust growth. Previous work has been undertaken to propose such a standardisation approach utilizing various measurements. For instance, it has already been suggested to use the variance [4], the min-max and z-score approaches of each individual, and such model that takes into consideration the parameters of each user for classifying other users [74].

A different phase of the research mostly on reliability or efficiency of blockchain-maintaining network nodes has also been carried out. To recognize the Bitcoin network's efficiency, Decker et al. experimentally observed that increasing network delays with PoW lead to expanded blockchain forks [28]. In 2014, Donet et al.

published a number of 872.648 IP addresses operating Bitcoin nodes and examined network stability and latency in the distribution of information [31]. Afterwards in 2018, Park et al. gathered Bitcoin network traffic for 39 days, evaluating territorial coverage, protocol client component, and network size (full-node vs. lightweight-node) [102]. More lately, Seol et al. suggested a traditional hierarchical structured blockchain design and lookup-chaining framework to boost blockchain's efficiency (TPS) while preserving the platform's centralised existence and facilitating simpler technology creation with blockchain [118]. Most plans were created to build blockchain-based applications and frameworks to take full advantage of its resources, such as infallibility, non-linearity, and decentralisation, and several further initiatives are ongoing to utilise the technology [5]. For instance, via blockchain [156] Xia et al. introduced a framework for configuring network access to medical records details. It utilises the authenticity of blockchain to monitor every person's access to sensitive information from healthcare workers, which also keeps records of such activities.

Usually, most of the current in E-commerce and IoT protection threat mitigation work is focused on the Intrusion Detection System (IDS) framework, which detects an attack utilising a centralised or distributed framework. In a centralised system [18], [99], where a single sensor-based IDS is installed as detection of attacks node on the IoT networks integrated to a central cloud, which categorises data traffic as an intrusion or normal scenario utilising a machine learning classifier model for the massive amount of data obtained from the whole network. Customers should trust an intrusion detection system (IDS), but the effect of trust must be evaluated incorporating machine learning and deep learning technology. The authors of [83] investigate the IDS system with machine learning to examine the trust effect of trustworthy of E-commerce.

The centralized cloud repository gathers a massive amount of data from various sensor nodes via the access point in the IoT network to improve the efficiency of

detecting attacks. Nevertheless, the development of data analytics on a wide scale is difficult because of the privacy problem with IoT apps or service providers. Possible data suppliers may not even be willing to identify their data because of the high probability of privacy breach. In fact, it requires a large number of transmission resources to collect a vast amount of data. In addition, the analysis of such a large quantity of data needs a tremendous deal of computing resources. From the other side, throughout the centralised framework for detecting attacks [29], data storage and analysis takes place in a distributed fashion rather than a central private cloud. It is the liability of each individual fog layer to gather and analyze their specific or private data by utilising a machine learning classifier to develop their own prototype of attack detection and then exchange the specific model with the remote implementation to enforce centralized detection attack mechanism.

Throughout this model, each node will not exchange its information with the SDN controller, due to data privacy being maintained at the stage of such nodes via blockchain. Furthermore, the need for higher transmission bandwidth is minimised due to the assumption that the data owner shares only the specification collection of the attack classification algorithm for each node. In comparison, computer processing to test the intrusion detection model is carried out in a clustered fashion with small samples collected from the fog layer via source implementation, this also produces lower latency based offloading computing. Thus having a quick response time due to computing closer to the trusted source. Nevertheless, the unified server sever has proper knowledge over the identification over threats in the distributed attack system. . In fact, each fog node needs an appropriate quantity of information in this design to allow effective identification of the threat. However, due to the very small number of network equipment involved with the cloud environment, or according to the security issues of smart devices, it is often hard to produce adequate data for the cloud server, leading to a lower degree of attack detection. This paper strengthens the centralised Attack Detection method to resolve this issue and

has a modern system of open and mutual monitoring of threats. Every single fog node in the complex framework has total control of its own.

Attack Protection Network, which is deployed with a variety of other nodes and an SDN based platform to mitigate the problem of a single point of failure and maintain appropriate data distribution. As a result, the distribution of the attack protection system provides an efficient sensed data detection system with insufficient data, which also improves the efficiency of the protection system. In order to develop and construct a new framework, we use the Ethereum blockchain network that enables peer-to-peer interactions or different sellers and buyers between nodes using a blockchain network to allow independent and collaborative attack detection [72]. In comparison, the latest architecture uses the SDN and the different node's computing paradigm to monitor and mitigate attacks with rapid reaction. Various findings on the deployment of SDN capabilities and blockchain have also been released to improve security in the various E-commerce based infrastructure. The DistBlockNet concept is applied in [124] by combining the advantages of blockchain technologies and SDN to include an efficient and secure IoT network architecture. Recently, we have deployed a ground-breaking SDN-based decentralized layered architecture for a distributed computing for E-commerce network aim of supporting adaptive, efficient, and trustworthy security to mitigate possible risks in the [123] decentralized system.

2.9 Blockchain

The blockchain developed from the bitcoin virtual money, a popular distributed ledger technology, and its benefits is primarily expressed in three components: decentralization, standardization, and flexibility. Scientists have shown that several examples can be extended to the blockchain. IBM established Adept with blockchain in the IoT domain to tackle the issue of centralized management. In ad-

Figure 2.1: Detailed Overview of TrustBlock [165].

dition to maintaining the normal connectivity with smart devices, Adept can also record the working state of enabled devices time, making it easier to control and trace compromised devices.

KSI utilized blockchain to include fundamental encryption for SDN in the area of network connectivity, and blockchain was used by the communication service provider to include information transmission and management services, such as certain key operations [98]. In the area of cloud services, [165] was built based on blockchain, which achieves low costs to maintain stability. Not only is the stability of Storj equal to high-end cloud services offerings, however, but the cost is also only 1–2 per cent of conventional cloud services. Such implementations are necessary to show the immense promise for the advancement of blockchain, which is used in our research model to test SDN’s nodes’ confidence.

2.9.1 Overview of TrustBlock

To address the above problems, this paper [165] recommends an SDN trust assessment method called TrustBlock. Involved groups, including consumers, SDNs, and validators, as seen in Figure 2.1. The user inserts the network packets to launch the forwarding task while the SDN operates. The data layer unit in the SDN comprises network nodes based on hardware and software. The double-layer benefits the trust attribute storage position that comprises some node capacity in the protocol stack

and is separated into two layers: the data block for node activity and the data block for node trust. Any client who wants to enter the trust level of an SDN data layer system (such as a newly approved user, previous user or SDN manager, etc.) is known as a validator, and any validator can see the trust level of any nodes at any point. Trust is gained in SDN by examining assessment points and suggesting third-party nodes. A node's trust value is not constant and can evolve based on the node's activities. Node I is the entity to be examined, and node j is the direct interaction node of I as seen in Figure 2.2, nodes k1, k2, and k3 are neighbour nodes within the general communication spectrum of nodes I and j. Node j will explicitly assess node I and implicitly assess by nearest neighbours. The detailed trust value of node I can be eventually achieved by averaging the historical trust value. Centred on this, three elements of specific trust (DTrust), indirect trust (ITrust), and historic trust (HTrust) measure the detailed trust (CTrust) of networks. Multiple variables impact node trust assessment in SDN. The principle and foundation of computing node faith is the creation of node trust schemes. A robust SDN node trust assessment framework should be developed by integrating consistency and protection in conjunction with the 'trust security + reliability' [151] definition. Figure 2.3 displays the final node confidence assessment method.

Figure 2.2: Interrelation of SDN based Nodes [165].

Figure 2.3: Detailed Overview of Trust Evaluation System with TrustBlock [165].

2.9.2 Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT)

A Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLTs) is a system that incorporates a ledger where information is saved with the help of central nodes. Xtian Cachin [19], the authors suggested a system where they were supporting for the usage of Byzantine approach as a simplistic method for introducing broadcasting with an atomic approach and maintaining the complete ordering of all transmitted data, provided the first basic components for the DLT. The key concept was the development of a tamper-proof ledger and the distribution of its power to all parties. There have been no fixed core nodes in BC-based networks, contrary to the clustered network layout. Consequently, once he has acquired enough power to get hold of the system, none of us can alter the data reported in the ledger. DLTs thus impose a degree of openness, quality control, and security by design [34].

In very various contexts, including such Internet of Things (IoT) [6], [16], the electoral system [8], was built based on machine to machine-based communication with the identification nodes on each entity [121]. These characteristics make them ideal for being a technology that improves stability, privacy, and integrity. DLTs are data structures at their heart whereby transactions can be registered, and a collection of functionalities to modify them. While each DLT uses various data structures and technology to distinguish itself, moreover, majority of DLTs systems are used in collaboration with very famous pillars, which are comprised on crypto algorithms with the public key, decentralised controlled P2P systems, and consensus-based

approaches [9]. The complexity for finding consensus between several participants in the network, only small trust between them is considered, due to this fact, is considered as Byzantine General's Dilemma" which was suggested in 1982 by computational scientists [73].

The complexity in evaluating the credibility of the exchanged messages between the generals motivated the authors to infer that computational model with fault tolerance is also optimised by using only one process to handle fault [40], the distributed consensus could not be achieved. Several consensus schemes have been developed to fix such an issue on the world wide web. Besides, there are multiple kinds of DLTs, as illustrated in [9]. The following technologies are currently created by BC [94], two other groups such as Tangle [136] and Hash Group [9]. BC is one of the most common and specialized DLT frameworks. Satoshi Nakamoto's proposal [94] to respond to the level of faith that arose in the finance market in 2007 as a consequence of the central management system [8]. Currently, in many complex domains, BC is being implemented.

2.9.3 Trust Evaluation with Blockchain Integration

Ensuring confidential data and non-repudiation are the key advantages of using the blockchain. In addition, blockchain still offers safe opportunities for connectivity and access control. Thus, it offers excellent opportunities to make the world of sellers and buyers more protected (an outline of potential security successful outcome is presented in [71] and [90]. Only a few publications [56], [78] grappling with protected storage and data integrity in respect to blockchain are used to incorporate blockchain in the field of E-commerce applications.

In a decentralised E-commerce application, controlling confidence scores is difficult due to the growing number of peers entering and exiting the system and their potential disruptive actions by deleting or modifying data that damages the system.

To measure the confidence score of an experienced provider or peer, the Trust Assessment Method is used. Most of the potential consumers become able to verify how much each of them can trust and can support an E-commerce platform provider based on this degree of trust. One challenge, as stated in the previous parts, is that the confidence data analysed may be modified or excluded from the system. In order to simplify the confidence management service's storage systems and ensure tamper-proof trust data, the authors [121] recommend that all measured trust data be preserved in the blockchain.

The blockchain interaction comprises several trust levels such as the Service-ID, the Service instances and the username of the Test-Agent. Such interactions are easily propagated toward the will be blockchain network portion of all peers and will also be part of a block. Then, to achieve any consensus on an equivalent variant from blockchain, this block must be validated by other peers. A summary of blockchain incorporation for the storage of confidence information is seen in Figure 2.4.

The literature offers many consensus frameworks to reach consensus for the validation of transactions and the formation of a block [21]. Proof of Work "PoW" [147] is the first verification method introduced in the blockchain. In attempting to solve a computational problem that needs the high computational capability to fix, the "PoW" consists of a network serving as "miners". The node that solves this puzzle first will verify it, later a new transactions block is added to the blockchain. To validate transactions and generating new block for BC for the first user [147], the performing behaviours are also utilised for validation.

2.10 Trust Evaluation Taxonomy

Most articles in the research categorise strategies to trust assessment based to their implementation contexts [150], [125]. The proposed solution was typically divided

Figure 2.4: E-commerce Nodes under DDoS Flood Attacks [67]

up into categories of trust assessment applicable to the network and those applicable to the Internet. Network implementations comprise [132] peer to peer (P2P) platforms, [114] multi-agent system structures, [125] social networks, and ad-Hoc frameworks [163]. In E-commerce application [61], and machine learning [96] are included as Internet applications based on trust model.

By evaluating the functional and efficiency actions of the new programmes they provide, the Trust Assessment Framework implemented in [5] includes an accurate means of measuring the trust score of peers. This methodology overcomes the shortcomings of many other trust schemes that, by validating the services, most of them are not capable to accept the initially generated trust factors and their associated values from the service providers or give a standard approval rate. This study suggests a Trust Assessment Framework incorporate all actions conducted by a peer representative such as buyers and sellers in the trust evaluation process, which analyses the resources rendered by a peer and examines the involvement of the peer in several E-commerce transaction-based tasks.

The name of this function is Test Agent. In time to enable a truly decentralised Trust Assessment Framework, by checking the features and actions of new services, all peers such as buyers and sellers' group can execute the tasks of the Test Agent. The motive behind completing these activities is the ability to improve the degree of self-confidence is used in buyers and sellers' group across many systems. In this research work, the Trust Assessment Method suggested comprises of 3 sections to assess a peer's trust score, including assessment from the Service Trust Evaluation, these are the potential services provided by the framework peer, conduct committed to continue-evaluates a peer's behaviour based on a service's authenticity; Activity Trust Evaluation also enables to evaluate test agents behaviour and status or other tasks conducted in the buyers and sellers transactions.

The Service Trust Assessment component aims at evaluating the service after im-

plementation to measure the preliminary trust score (System Checking), constantly tracking service activity and performance on the basis of many criteria, and considering the ranking of a service conducted by all M2 M member peers on the basis of their very own knowledge. The reliability of service records, such as trust details or service specifications, is reviewed in the Behavioural Trust Assessment section and the peer making these improvements is low rating in the event of adjustments. The part of the Task Confidence Assessment consists of tracking the number of research activities carried out by a colleague who serves as a test agent. The more important evaluation tasks are conducted by an individual with the higher the client's confidence level. In addition to evaluating operations, there is also the ability for Task Trust Assessment to consider certain operations.

2.10.1 Application-Based Trust Evaluation Model

The Eigen Trust framework is designed by [66] in Network infrastructures, and the "universal" values of trust factor associated with model's nodes determined in term of accumulating binary scores trust evaluation. A PeerTrust equation that shows certain general trust parameters and calculations to integrate ratings into a specific trust value was proposed by [159]. Marsh [1994] suggests a theoretical model of trust in multi-agent systems, which is known as the earliest study on trust in information technology. The trust property (i.e., context-based and propogative) is implemented in Marsh's computer program. Trust propagation is an interesting matter in social networks. The authors in [43] suggest conditional rating-based trust distribution architectures. Present trust mechanisms in ad hoc applications are structured to model the domains with higher trust factors by utilising their associated transaction history and trustful information [80] and distributing secure packets [171]. [151] suggest several confidence evaluation metrics in the field of Service-Oriented Computing (SOC) and a trust computation algorithm, which enables to calculate the trust score. The authors in RATE-Web [86] model consolidates the customer's

rating scores and seeks to promote the preference of a provider with trust-related factors. Based on the response, a network service's global trust is computed by [47].

2.10.2 Technique Based Trust Evaluation Model

Based on the suggested taxonomy approach for techniques based, the authors in [25] and [125], provide support to categorise strategies to trust assessment as per the trust system method implemented.

1. **Legacy Security Technique** - Nevertheless, the trust factor in E-commerce is security-related, and standard mechanisms to implement security and validation, such as verification, authentication, and regulation of accessibility can also be implemented for the development of trust. For instance, [25] suggested a method focused on credential-based access control and trust protection to protect data access, authors suggest a database, where a security-based framework incorporates the regulations to measure cloud provider trust.
2. **Heuristic Approach** - The trust testing models that adopt heuristic-based frameworks seek to establish a practical structure which is easy to comprehend and construct [125]. The proposed mechanisms are also ideal for applications with significant numbers of potential users. Several of the heuristic-based methods, from a statistical viewpoint, is to quantify and aggregate numerical input scores. The authors proposed various formulas in [158], [86], [151], for instance, measure the total or proportional scores. In contrast, the studies in [25] and [150] suggest another well-developed accumulation approaches that take full advantage of fuzzy structures to assess the trustworthiness of goals by using membership functions.
3. **Machine Learning or Statistical Approach** - The approaches focused on machine learning model for statistical analysis reflect on developing a rational

computational formula for the trust information and management. Usually, two main instances focused on statistical theory are Bayesian structures [39] and the conditional opinion model [61], [24]. In the machine learning model, mainly Artificial Neural Network (ANN) [137] and hidden Markov models (HMMs) are [57] in the other direction, implemented for trust analysis. The conditional probability model is used in , which also incorporates the valuable trust factors and values withing E-commerce platforms for millions of users.

4. **Information theory-based Approach** - There is a significant difference in the online marketplace about committed knowledge, such as quality of the product, and the real findings of buyers. [25] suggest a series of principles to describe participation and implementation (observation) from the viewpoint of the theory of information, as well as principles such as credibility. Likewise, in social networking sites, [3] use entropy to quantify "conversation equilibrium" between two users and describe their framework as a function of confidence dependent on actions.

2.11 Summary

This chapter presents the general research concerns related to trust evaluation, trust management, context aware trust evaluation model and Block chain-based security framework for E-commerce applications. Firstly, we present different level of trust evaluation models and its related issues. In various existing research studies, most of the authors mainly focusing on the issue of physical interaction which is not present in E-commerce. To overcome the lack of such physical interaction in E-commerce industries, existing studies utilise some special trust dimensions and contexts aware model to improve the trust. Secondly, our research comprehensively depicts some security level issues in E-commerce applications. Such as single point failure which can lead to disruption of entire system. To overcome this, this chapter also presents

the existing research studies with the help of trust function of blockchain security framework in SDN context.

Chapter 3

Multi-Dimensional E-commerce

Trust Evaluation Method

3.1 Introduction

According to [64] trustworthiness can be equated with a social context in some ways – for example, by referring to the interaction history, social trust, word of mouth from a reliable third party, or certification, etc., of a concept, person, product, or service.

There are many models have proposed by researchers depending on only the past transactions to represent the trust of a seller [2]. However, most of these models show only the general status of trust while the buyer might have concerns about the new transactions. The buyers might not rely on this trust value, which only infers to the trust level of a past transaction. As a result, the buyers might be vulnerable to be attacked by malicious sellers. For example, a good trust of a malicious seller can be simply built up by selling cheap products or services and then starting cheating the buyers after obtaining a good trust , [59] . This kind of attack has been mentioned and named by [68] as the value imbalance problem.

This work proposes a method that can be used to evaluate the contextual trust that can prevent the value imbalance problem by identifying the malicious transaction. This method is mainly based on three dimensions (the sold product type dimension, the number of product sold dimension and the transaction amount dimension) which play the main roles in term of explaining the contexts of transaction. It also can be used in term of measuring the similarity between the past transactions and the new transaction. This chapter shows some models which take in the consideration the relationship between the similarity evaluation and the trust evaluation. It also shows the methodology that is used in the proposed method and how this method works.

3.2 Multi-Dimensional E-commerce Trust Evaluation Method Based on Contexts, Inheritance and Similarity

In this work, a trust evaluation method is applied in e-services environment (e.g. e-commerce). It is generally based on the comparisons within three dimensions; a) the similarity between the products types, the similarity between the number of the item sold (T_{TN}) and the similarity of the transactions amounts (T_{AM}) which play the most important role in the explanation of the transaction contexts. The final trust value (T_{Final}) is identified as follows:

$$T_{Final} = \frac{T_{TN} + T_{AM}}{2} \quad (3.1)$$

There are some contextual properties of any online transaction such as products and services tree, the number of products sold and transaction amount which are considered as one of the main properties. Therefore, they have major impacts on

establishing the trust between the users in e-commerce websites. The products and services types of trees in the e-commerce website can also assist the users to make the transactions in trustworthy environments. Additionally, the transaction amount dimension plays an important role in the trust evaluation because the buyers might have concerns if the seller starts selling a new product which is already in the same tree that he/she used to sell but in a higher or a lower prices which can create a possibility to commit fraud.

3.3 Trust Evaluation Method based on Product Type Similarity

This section shows the first factor in the proposed method (T_{TN}) that can be used to measure the similarity between the product types in addition to the number of the products sold within the proposed tree as shown in Figure 3.3.

3.3.1 The Modified Products and Services Tree ($MTree_{ps}$)

There are some existing categorizations which are used to divide the products in the market into groups such as eCl@ss [51]. eCl@ss is considered as a hierarchical classification which uses an ontology structure that includes a four-level hierarchy. Each level is represented by two characters numerical value while the last level is enriched with a set of attributes. The used tree in this method is created based on eCl@ss. In the addition to the products types, we added the number of item sold and the price of every sold item. The tree has the number of levels and every level has a code which is taken from eCl@ss and the price range of selling every item as shown in Figure 3.3.

3.3.2 The similarity between the products types (T_{TN}) within $MTree_{ps}$

To find the similarity between the items within the tree we created the graph using a hyperbolic tangent function as shown in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: The relationship between the similarity value and the level of products

The Figure 3.1 used to depict the co-relation and relationship between the similarity value and the level of products, with the help of relationship in between enables to classify and evaluate the trust factors based on suggested equations 3.2, 3.3, 3.4.

To find the similarity between the items within $MTree_{ps}$ we created the following logarithmic graph as shown in Figure 3.1. In order to evaluate the trust value within $MTree_{ps}$, this method suggests the following formula:

$$T_{tn(Final)} = T_{tn(level1)} + T_{tn(level2)} + \dots + T_{tn(levelx)} \quad (3.2)$$

To find the trust value of every level $T_{tn(levelx)}$, this method suggests the following

equation

$$T_{tn(level)} = \frac{N_{pc}}{N_{total}} * Dis_{level} \quad (3.3)$$

While N_{pc} is a number of a specific product sold in the specific level, N_{total} is a number of all products that have been sold in the specific level and Dis_{level} is the distance between the levels which can be obtained by using the following formula:

$$Dis_{level(x)} = SIM_{level(x+1)} - SIM_{level(x)} \quad (3.4)$$

Where SIM_{level} is identified by using the hyperbolic tangent function as shown in Figure 3.1.

$$SIM_{level} = \tanh(level) \quad (3.5)$$

3.4 Trust Evaluation Method based on Transaction Amount Similarity

The transaction amount is another important dimension which plays an important role in the transaction context in order to establish a trustworthy relationship between two nodes in the e-commerce environment. As shown in Figure 3.2, there are two scenarios in term of measuring the similarity between the new transaction amount and the past transactions amounts to evaluate the trust value.

1st Scenario: The new transaction is on selling a product that has been sold and it is in the seller products tree. In this case, there are some cases that are needed to be considered in order to evaluate the trust value in the transaction amount dimension.

The new transaction amount is in between the minimum and the maximum amount of all transactions amounts that are made by the seller. As shown in Equation 3.6

3.4. TRUST EVALUATION METHOD BASED ON TRANSACTION AMOUNT SIMILARITY

Figure 3.2: the influence of transaction amount on trust value

$$Min \leq X \leq Max; T_{AM} = 1 \quad (3.6)$$

In this case, the similarity between the new transaction amount and the past transactions amounts will be considered as in the highest level. As a result, the trust value will be considered as the highest value which is “ONE”.

Case 1: The new transaction amount is less than the minimum amount in the past transactions. In this case, this method suggests “Lower Range (LR)” which is 25% of the minimum amount of the past transactions. There are two scenarios that can happen listed as follows:

- a) The new transaction is in between the minimum amount and the lower range (LR), as shown in Equation 3.7.

$$LR < X < Min \quad (3.7)$$

In the case, the trust value between the transaction and the past transactions is identified as expressed in Equation 3.8

$$T_{AM} = \frac{X - LR}{Min - LR} \quad (3.8)$$

b) The new transaction is equal or less than the lower range of the minimum amount, as shown in Equation 3.9.

$$X \leq LR; T_{AM} = 0 \quad (3.9)$$

In this case, the trust value between the new transaction amount and the past transactions amounts will be considered as “Zero” because there is no similarity between them.

Case 2: The new transaction amount is higher than the maximum amount in the past transactions. In this case, this method suggests “Upper Range (UR)” which is 10% of the maximum amount of the past transactions. There are two scenarios that can happen listed as follows: a) The new transaction is in between the maximum amount and the Upper range (UR), as shown in Equation 3.10.

$$Max < X < UR \quad (3.10)$$

In the case, the trust value between the transaction and the past transactions is identified as expressed in Equation 3.2

$$T_{AM} = \frac{X - Max}{Max - UR} \quad (3.11)$$

b) The new transaction is equal or higher than the upper range (UR) of the maximum amount, as shown in Equation 3.12.

$$X \leq UR; T_{AM} = 0 \quad (3.12)$$

In this case, the trust value between the new transaction amount and the past transactions amounts will be considered as “Zero” because there is no similarity between them.

2nd Scenario:

The new transaction is on selling a product that has not been sold and it is not in the seller products tree. Although there is a similarity between the new transaction amount and the amount of the past transaction, the trust value is less than “ONE”. The reason for that, the seller has not been in any transactions in selling this new product, so the trust value should be lesser than if the new transaction is made in the same product as well as the same amount. Additionally, as discussed in the last section, a seller can sell the same product in the same amount, so he/she should obtain the higher value than if he/she starts making a new transaction by selling a different product or different amount. This method is to prevent this kind of problem which is “the value imbalance problem”. Therefore, the trust value should be decreased if the seller starts selling a new product or being in any transaction with a different amount. As a result, in order to prevent this kind of problem, this method considers “P” as a penalty of lacking the experience in selling the new product using the following formula 3.13.

$$P = 1 - SIM_{level1} \quad (3.13)$$

Where SIM_{level} is a similarity which is obtained by using the hyperbolic tangent function as discussed in the last section and shown in Figure 3.1.

There are some cases taken into account in order to evaluate the trust value dis-

cussed below:

Case 1:

The new transaction amount is in between the minimum and the maximum amount, as shown in Equation 3.14.

$$Min \leq X \leq Max; T_{AM} = 1 - P \quad (3.14)$$

In this case, the similarity between the new transaction amount and the past transactions amounts will be considered as in the highest level after applying P.

Case 2:

The new transaction amount is less than the minimum amount. In this case, this method suggests “Lower Range (LR)” which is the percentage of the minimum amount. There are two scenarios that can happen listed as follows: a) The new transaction is in between the minimum amount and the lower range (LR), as shown in Equation 3.15.

$$LR \leq X \leq Min \quad (3.15)$$

In the case, the trust value between the transaction and the past transactions, as shown in Equation 3.16.

$$T_{AM} = \frac{X - LR}{Min - LR} - P \quad (3.16)$$

b) The new transaction is equal or Lower than the lower range of the minimum amount , as shown in Equation 3.17.

$$X \leq LR; T_{AM} = 0 \quad (3.17)$$

In this case, the trust value between the new transaction amount and the past transactions amounts will be considered as “Zero” because there is no similarity between them.

Case 3: The new transaction amount is higher than the maximum amount. In this case, this method suggests “Upper Range (UR)” which is the percentage of the maximum amount. There are two scenarios that can happen listed as follows:

a) The new transaction is in between the maximum amount and the Upper range (UR), as shown in Equation 3.18.

$$Max \leq X \leq UR \quad (3.18)$$

In this case, the trust value is shown in Equation 3.19.

$$T_{AM} = \frac{X - Max}{Max - UR} - P \quad (3.19)$$

b) The new transaction is equal or higher than the upper range (UR) of the maximum amount , as shown in Equation 3.20.

$$UR \leq X; T_{AM} = 0 \quad (3.20)$$

In this case the trust value between the new transaction amount and the past transactions amounts will be considered as “Zero” because there is no similarity

between them.

3.5 Results and discussion

Example 1: Assume that a seller is going to make a new transaction by selling a fax machine. Following the proposed method, fax as a machine is in the level four in $MTree_{ps}$, so there are three factors need to be measured in level one, level two, level three as well as level four.

Factor 1: the number of product sold N_{pc} in every level which are 100 transactions in level one, 70 transactions in level two, 30 transactions in level three and 30 transactions in level four.

Factor 2: the Trust value in every level $T_{tn(level)}$ with measuring the distance Dis_{level} between the similarities in every level SIM_{level} as expressed in equation 3.4 . $T_{tn(level(1))} = 0.65$, $T_{tn(level(2))} = 0.175$, $T_{tn(level(3))} = 0.08$ and $T_{tn(level(4))} = 0.01$

Factor 3: the final trust value $T_{tn(final)}$ which is obtained by using the suggested formula as expressed in equation 3.2 so $T_{tn(Final)} = 0.915$ which is considered as a high value and this is because the seller has a good experience in selling Fax and he/she has sold all the required transactions in every level.

Example 2: Assume that a seller is going to make a new transaction by selling Laser Printer. Following the proposed method, Laser Printer as a product is in level four in $MTree_{ps}$.

Factor 1: the number of product sold N_{pc} in every level which are 100 transactions in level one, 30 transactions in level two, 30 transactions in level three and 0 transaction in level four.

Factor 2: tthe Trust value in every level $T_{tn(level)}$ with measuring the distance

Dis_{level} between the similarities in every level SIM_{level} as expressed in equation 3.4 . $T_{tn(level(1))} = 0.65$, $T_{tn(level(2))} = 0.075$ $T_{tn(level(3))} = 0.08$ and $T_{tn(level(4))} = 0$ as no transaction has not been made in selling Laser Printer.

Factor 3: the final trust value $T_{tn(final)}$ which is obtained by using the suggested formula as expressed in equation 3.2 so $T_{tn(Final)} = 0.805$ which is considered as a good value. Although the seller has not made a transaction in selling this product, the product “Laser Printer” is still in his category as he sold 100 transactions in the same category which means he/she should be trustworthy in selling this type of product unless the amount of transaction has a bit different which will be discussed in explaining the influence of the transaction amount dimension.

Example 3: Assume the seller is going to make a new transaction by selling something, not in his category which means he/she has not sold before (let’s say Tobacco). Following the proposed method, the seller has gained $T_{tn(level)} = 0$ in the all levels in the tree as he/she has not made any transaction in this category which is completely different from his/her category. As a result, there is a big possibility for the fraud to happen (the value imbalance problem), so the proposed method can prevent this kind of problem by giving the seller’s final trust value $T_{tn(final)} = 0$ which means he/she is not trustworthy in selling this type of product.

In summary, the proposed method can be used to measure the similarity between the products types and the number of the product sold. Additionally, in order to make this method more accurate, there is a huge need to add the transactions amounts as another dimension to it which has been discussed above. To clarify it, we used the last examples with this dimension (the transactions amounts). Assume that, the seller is going to make a new transaction in selling “Laser Printer” for £140. It can be seen that this product “Laser Printer” is not in the seller category as shown in Figure 3.3, and there is no transaction has been made in selling Laser Printer. The new transaction amount is £140 which is in between the minimum

amount and the maximum transaction amount which were made in the level of Laser Printer. Following the proposed method, this transaction amount is expressed as $Min \leq X \leq Max$ as discussed above. However, this product "Laser Printer" is considered as a new product, so the proposed method suggests "P" as a penalty of lacking the experience in selling this new product which is expressed in equation 3.13. $P = 0.02$. therefore, the trust value of this new transaction amount of "Laser Printer" is less than ONE because this seller has not sold Laser Printer before but he/she has sold many products which are located in the same category of Laser Printer as shown in Figure 3.3. The trust value of this transaction amount $T_{AM} = 0.96$ after applying the penalty (P) due to the seller's lack of experience in selling Laser Printer.

Figure 3.3: The Modified Products and Services Tree ($MTree_{ps}$)

In order to evaluate the final trust value T_{Final} with the last examples by following the proposed method as expressed in Equation 4.1, T_{Final} of selling Fax = 0.75 which is considered as "Excellent" as shown in the Table 3.1. The reason of that is

Table 3.1: Rating Scores Categorizations

Poor	Medium	Good	Excellent
$0 \leq T < 0.25$	$0.25 \leq T < 0.5$	$0.5 \leq T < 0.75$	$0.75 \leq T \leq 1$

the seller has made 30 transactions in selling Fax which obtains 0.915 in the first dimension T_{TN} but the new transaction amount of selling Fax is £260 is higher than his/her normal range in the same level four (Fax's level) which is (£50 - £250), so he/she obtains 0.6 in the transaction amount dimension (T_{AM}) which affects his/her T_{Final} value. In order to evaluate the final trust value, T_{Final} with the last examples by following the proposed method as expressed in equation 4.1, T_{Final} of selling Laser Printer is 0.88 which is considered as "Excellent" as shown in the Table 3.1. Although, the seller has not made any transaction in selling Laser Printer, he/she obtains 0.805 in the first dimension T_{TN} , this is because he sold many transactions in the same category of Laser Printer and the new transaction amount of selling Laser Printer (£140) is in the normal range in the same level four (Laser Printer's level) which is (£50 - £250), so he/she obtains 0.96 in T_{AM} . Every e-commerce website has trust ratings scores which represents the final trust value of every seller. These scores are calculated using the given ratings by the buyers after every transaction. These scores are usually a set of numbers for example the rating scores which is in eBay [-1 ,0 ,1]. While epinions ¹ shows the scores as an integer [0,1,2,3,4,5]. According to [75] the numerical values which is in 0,1 are more appropriate in order to evaluate the trust value. Therefore, this chapter categorised the final trust value to five scales listed as shown in the Table 3.1:

3.6 Summary

In this chapter, the proposed method is considered as a contextual trust evaluation method as it takes into account some contexts of any transaction (product type,

¹<http://www.epinions.com>

number of product sold and transaction amount). This method can assist to prevent the value imbalance problem by measuring the similarity between three dimensions (contexts) and evaluating the final trust value. In fact, there are many online consumers have suffered from monetary loose problem due to some reasons which the lack of the trust in e-commerce is one of them.

For example, some of them can easily build a good reputation by making many transactions by selling cheap products with good qualities and start to commit frauds by selling more expensive products. This kind of frauds is named by [68] as the value imbalance problem. Therefore, there is a great demand for a trust evaluation mechanism which consider the new transaction as well as the past transactions. In this chapter, we propose a new method which considers three dimensions that play important roles in any online transaction to help the buyers to detect the frauds. This method measures the similarity between the new transaction and the past transactions in the products types dimension, the number of the products sold dimension and the transactions amounts dimension.

Chapter 4

Trust Model for Value Imbalance

Problem based on Transaction

Time and Ratings

4.1 Introduction

The demand has changed because of the emergence of modern digital technological advances. The Internet is a social network connecting millions of citizens and companies around the globe, creating a digital platform with enormous economic opportunities E-busines. More businesses are realizing the benefits while using the Internet as a communications medium to meet customers at any location on the globe.

However, one of the main reasons that customers have experienced money loss due to the lack of trust in internet business which takes the digital market to a constant need for some system that analyses trust through online transactions. Some e-commerce websites use an existing trust management system that measures the seller's trust value by evaluating the trust based on past transaction ratings. So,

the possibility of fraud being committed is increased by some of the malicious people because trust status can only reflect the general trust status without taking the new transactions into the account. For instance, some of them can rapidly build a good image by selling great quality, modest items with the goal that they can make more sales and start committing fraud by selling more costly items. This sort of misrepresentation is utilized as the imbalance problem values [68].

Followed by the aforementioned issues in Chapter 3 , as already discussed in Chapter 3, some of existing research failed to provide fully functional method to play important roles in any online transaction to help the buyers to detect the frauds by measuring the similarity between the new transaction and the past transactions in the product types dimension. To overcome such challenges, this chapter provides the effective method to deal such fraud. However, there is an alarming demand to create a trust evaluation based model that provides feasible support for both current and past sales [69]. The trust and reputation factors are manipulated and processed with the help of a local cache application.

The proposed model can be applied for e-commerce applications such as eBay for reliable and effective trust assessment [116], this model is created based on local cache that provides an authenticity attribute by avoiding data exploitation. The proposed model is capable to normalise several user's evaluations after following their evaluation criteria, which continuously changes with time [48] . This model also investigates trust and reputation for all users based on the general merchant rating and the aspects of the transaction amount, both have a significant role in any online transaction to help customers gain trust in online shopping and identify the frauds.

We propose this model for effectively measuring credibility and confidence values from a transaction records and ranking information in this presented design. We maintain the information on the local cache-based trust mechanism because it's

immutable, but our model doesn't parse all of the existing transaction details on each transaction update because as sending and processing all data of transactions values can lead to in effective and slower process. Instead, we have used a small buffer of key values to speed up queries while still authenticating and checking certain values in the context for accuracy. The objective of using local cache-based trust system is to verify the Transaction Time and Ratings and associated data, as well as to validate the notion of time in calculations with large amounts of data. Our framework can extract accurate credibility and trust values from user ratings, which may be helpful for consumers making choices when purchasing or offering product lines on the Website. Additionally, those values may aid both vendors and buyers in avoiding suspicious activities.

4.2 Design and Method of Trust Evaluation

There have been three major issues to address when interacting with thousands of transaction analyses. Firstly, a lot of system memory and processing capacity is required to look up transaction details for each main source while modifying the current value. It is therefore important to build a system that needs only a limited footprint of transaction records in the local cache for quick updates. Second, consumer behaviour and perceptions typically constantly evolve. It is also essential to keep records of the seasonal fluctuations of and person's determination requirements over the duration, considering the periods and the volume of transactions. Finally, the filtering of the accumulated values by low pass filtering is important to consider the general pattern of each user's ranking tendency rather than individual instances. In order to address these constraints and successfully extract meaning from credibility and trust, our model has four mathematical metrics to evaluate trust based on personal evaluation criteria (PEC), the similarity between the transactions times (T_{Ti}), overall ratings of the sellers (S'_{Ra}) and Modified Products and

Services Tree $MTree_{ps}$. After utilising such features and normalisation, the model extracts the credibility and confidence of each seller and consumer.

In this work, the trust evaluation method is proposed, which widely used in e-commerce-based applications. Normally this method is used to evaluate the similarities between the transactions within two dimensions; the similarity between the transactions times (T_{Ti}), and the overall ratings of the sellers that were given by the buyers (S'_{Ra}) which play important roles in the explanation of the transaction contexts. Transaction time is one of the main contexts of any online transaction, also it refers to the time slot, once a transaction is made by seller. The trust evaluation method is also called time-sensitive method, due to fact that the seller is capable to modify his/her behaviour with time by selling something more expensive than what he/she used to sell after building a good trust which is our targeted problem (the value imbalance problem). Transaction time also posses a specific feature of trust computation. Each query from temporal dimension is considered as the buyer's query for such as (from April 2019 until June 2019) because the buyer might have a concern if the seller has sold this item or not in a specific period of time. The final trust value (T_{Final}) is derived by dividing the sum of the value of transaction times similarity and the overall rating by 2 as the average which is identified as follows:

$$T_{Final} = \frac{T_{Ti} + S'_{Ra}}{2} \quad (4.1)$$

There are some qualitative features of any electronic purchase, such as transaction time and the date during the buyer and seller transaction. Thus, this plays a very vital role to create the trust created between potential users of E-commerce websites, due to fact that some sellers only initiate selling very basic and cheap products and stop selling them after building good trusts. However, the seller either sells the desired goods or not, but customers may have various concerns for such products.

4.2.1 Personal Evaluation Criteria (PEC)

Each person has a particular capacity to analyse. For example, some might be more supportive or stringent in the measurement, and others may have lower or higher-grade distinctions than the others. To locate the performance evaluation pattern, we suggest a personal evaluation criteria (PEC) formula based on an average and the variance of the evaluation scores of each customer. Our model changes these properties for any transaction made and stores them in a local cache that can be checked at any period by analysing the database of the transaction in the repository. By retaining these characteristics, the framework can normalise calculations in regular frequency, and it becomes pointless to look at all activities of the user and figure out the intention of the consumer and analyse their E-commerce related activities.

$$\begin{aligned}
 PEC_{Avg}W.tx^t &= \sum_{\alpha.W.tx^t}^{e^t} PEC_{Avg}W.tx(t-1) \\
 &(1 - \alpha W.tx^t(td(t))) \tag{4.2} \\
 t &= init
 \end{aligned}$$

In Equation 4.2, our proposed model utilises the average PEC for every transaction input, where e^t is used for latest transaction value for evaluation. The term PEC_{Avg} is also used to maintain the long-lasting average values for all current records, $\alpha.W.tx^t$ depicts the self-adaptive parameters to utilise the time spans for all inputs. Equation 4.2 evaluates the most recent PEC discrepancy, that measures the degree of variance in performance grades. PEC average is close to 0 unless the user evaluates the activity for the first instance and there is no prior assessment of the comparison. Anything other than that, the same approach as PEC average is used to maintain track of the progress to the appraisal values.

4.2.2 The Modified Products and Services Tree $MTree_{ps}$

There are some fundamental existing classifiers, which can be utilized to classify business products according to categories such as eCl@ss. The eCl@ss is known as a hierarchical class, which is used with a system of ontology on four different levels. Each level is denoted by two characters based discrete values, while a set of attributes enriches the final level. In this strategy, the tree is developed followed by an eCl@ss. Concerning the commodity categories, we included the number of items sold and the cost of each item sold. The tree is divided into several levels, where each level contains a code that is generated by using eCl@ss and the price range of each product being sold as seen in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1: $MTree_{ps}$

4.2.3 Transaction Time Similarity T_{Ti}

As stated earlier, transaction time T_{Ti} is a dimension that plays a vital role in the sense of the transaction to create a trust correlation between two nodes of the E-commerce applications. Trust determination is time-sensitive since the consistency of each transaction can vary over time. The transaction time dimension has a specific characteristic of trust calculation. For example, a time aspect question will start from a preceding point, such as six months ago, and the current ending

time. Thus the transaction time dimension is a complex dimension that should be considered in the frameworks of trust evaluation. This section shows how to calculate the trust value, which comprises various scenarios, also depicted in Figure 4.2, In terms of calculating the similarities among the current transaction duration and previous transaction periods, there are two possibilities exist to determine the trust value.

1st Scenario: Once any item that was sold and that's in the tree of merchant items, then for this situation, there are a few situations that could have been included in the transaction time aspect for determining the trust value.

Case 1:The merchant has made a transaction in selling the item between the minimum time (present) and the maximum time (6 months ago).

$$Min \leq X \leq Max; T_{Ti} = 1$$

In this case, as at the highest level, the transaction similarity between the current time and the previous time will be considered as a feasible factor. Moreover, the trust value is considered as the highest value that seems to be "ONE."

Case 2: The seller made a transaction to sell the item yet once in a while after the Max time (6 months ago). For this situation, this strategy recommends "Upper Range (UR)" which consists 10% of the Max time. Therefore, two situations can exist as follows:

a) The seller has made the transaction in the middle of the Max time and the Upper Range (UR).

$$Max < X < UR$$

For the situation, the trust factor between the new transaction and the previous

transaction is recognized as follows:

$$T_{Ti} = \frac{x - Max}{Max - UR} \quad (4.3)$$

b) The transaction time initiated from the dealer is equal or higher than maximum time in the upper range of time.

$$UR \leq X; T_{Ti} = 0$$

For this situation, Zero is considered as the trust value between the new transaction made and the previous transactions, because no similarity exists between them.

Figure 4.2: The transaction time influence on trust value

2nd Scenario: The particular item that has not been sold by the same seller, however, he/she has sold another item in a similar category of the new item. In this way, there may be a relationship of similarity between the new transaction time and the previous transaction periods yet the trust values calculation of the new transaction must be less than ONE. The explanation behind this, the merchant did not sell the same item, which is in the purchaser's inquiry or transactions, where the value of the trust would be less than if the new transaction for the same time period is reported within the same item. Also, as discussed in the last section, a seller may

have sold a similar item in a similar time-frame, therefore, he/she has to get a higher value except when he/she initiate a new transaction to sell different product ranges across different time series. This approach is intended to avoid this form of problem, known as the value mismatch problem. But, if the merchant continues selling another commodity or is interested in another deal within the various time periods, the trust factor will be decreased. As a consequence, this approach deals 'P' as the limited experience for such selling ranges, the new item utilizing the below equation to avoid such type of problem:

$$P = 1 - SIM_{level}$$

Where SIM_{level} depicts the relationship of similarity between the new item categories and the item which is in the same tree category of seller. SIM_{level} is collected based on a hyperbolic tangent feature, and also presented in the logarithmic chart in 4.3.

Figure 4.3: The relationship between the different level of products with similarity.

There are certain situations that can be feasibly utilised for the evaluation of the trust value as discussed below:

Case 1: When selling the product, the seller has made a contract between the minimum time and the maximum time (6 months).

$$Min \leq X \leq Max; T_{Ti} = 1 - P$$

In this case, the trust relation between the new transaction and previous transactions will be assumed as the highest level after using P.

Case 2: Once the seller initiates the transaction for the selling another item, however most the time after reaching the limit of the purchaser's inquiry. For this situation, this technique recommends "Upper Range (UR)" which stood at 10% of the Max time (over last 6 months). In this manner, there are two situations that can be established, which are provided as follows:

a) The seller has made the transaction in the middle of the Max time level and the Upper Range (UR) level.

$$Max < X < UR$$

In this case, the trust value between the current transaction and the previous transactions can be calculated by following equation:

$$T_{Ti} = \frac{X - UR}{Max - UR} - P \quad (4.4)$$

b) The processing time of the seller's transaction is equal to or higher than the maximum time's limit.

$$UR \leq X; T_{Ti} = 0$$

For this case, as there is no correlation between the current transaction and previous transactions, therefore trust value should be considered as Zero.

4.2.4 Considering the Overall Rating of a seller (S'_{Ra})

The overall ratings of the sellers that were given by the buyers (S'_{Ra}) which plays a significant role in the transaction contexts explanation. This method considers the overall rating (S'_{Ra}) by simply converting the shown rating of the seller on eBay which is a percentage to a number to include it as a factor in the final equation, for example, if (S'_{Ra}) of the seller is 91%, it will be 0.91 in the final equation.

4.3 Proposed System with Caching

Figure 4.4: Proposed System for Trust and Reputation with Local Cache Illustration.

Our system design is based on the local cache-based online transaction, that allows users to buy goods, place orders, and transfer funds. In particular, the framework enables the active participants to assess one another based on their satisfaction with each activity. The proposed system stores not only the transaction data but also the 'rank' details as well, which is stored in the caching memory. From local cache memory, where each node is connected to their respective transactions with each

transaction is authenticated as though it were a payment of its own with its online transaction. When we have transaction and ranking details in the database, trust and confidence can be feasibly determined easily by analyzing that information and utilising our methodology. We have developed our design with a test framework for online transactions by using local cache technology.

The proposed model has authenticity and, thus, information is protected and secured. Nevertheless, these might take significant amounts of measurement and time to parse the whole nodes for each transaction change. For this purpose, in every transaction modification that has happened, we proposed to use a local cache that needs only a short lifespan of core attributes for quick updates without the need to analyse all preceding transaction data. However, due to factors including such device refresh, network disconnection, or even interference, there is a possibility of local cache falling out-of-sync with the initial local cache Database. Our framework regularly validates and authenticates the cache data in the background for stability without degrading the user interface to overcome this problem. If some difference is detected between the cache and the records, the cache is bypassed by incoming knowledge extracted from the perspective Database. This is focused on the principle that we use a local cache because consensus has been established and the longer chain has been assigned, an inviolable and permanent distributed ledger. This frequent reset and upgrade happen after 5 minutes in our demonstration, in contrast to when a user upgrade is activated by the system admin. Even so, depending on the program condition and the demand on the device, this time is configured based on users' transactions. This design is illustrated in Figure 4.4, in which the cache is modified from the Database consistently. Rather than just parsing the whole model data, the user may use the cache for short query answers, which may take a little time relative to the amount of information.

To provide an overview of the effect of using the cache, we calculated the average latency of the transaction modification (including trust and credibility calculation)

on our system using the benchmark used in the last section. Both Figure 4.5 and Figure 4.6 show the distribution of these latency statistics with local cache and without local cache. Figure 4.5 depicts the distribution of latency statistics without local cache approach and Figure 4.6 shows the distribution of latency statistics with the local cache. The two figures which look identical but remember the x-axis units; they are distinct in magnitude orders (seconds vs. milliseconds). This illustrates how important it is to include the cache while analysing the data in the Database of the model.

Figure 4.5: Latency Distribution without local cache for Trust Evaluation

Overall, Figure 4.5 shows that average latency for PEC and MTree metrics achieve around 60% of latency at a frequency of 20, after sharp decline these metrics again exponentially increase up to 80% of latency at a frequency of 45. At frequency 20 and 45, S'_{Ra} and T_{Ti} metrics achieve nearly 90% of overhead. Moreover, the distribution of latency statistics without a local cache approach has significantly higher processing overhead as compared to the model with a local cache approach.

In Figure 4.6 average latency for PEC and (T_{Ti}) metrics achieve around 45% of latency at a frequency of 20, after sharp decline these metrics again reaches up to 40% of latency at a frequency of 42. At frequency 20 and 45, S'_{Ra} and MTree

Figure 4.6: Latency Distribution with local cache for Trust Evaluation

metrics achieve nearly 70% of average overhead. Moreover, the distribution of latency statistics with a local cache approach has lower processing overhead as compared to the model without a local cache approach. Also, the system with local cache is significantly faster, which consumes fewer resources as well.

4.4 Results Evaluation of Proposed Model

To validate the feasibility of the proposed design for the derivation of trust and confidence factors, we first perform tests with a sample from eBay dataset composed of different types of users. We equate our credibility and trust values with the help of widely used average naive cumulative raw assessment, which is mostly used all, E-commerce applications to assess the average scores on www.ebay.com, www.epinions.com, etc. We assume that the naive cumulative average of the raw assessment will not represent well the time element and individual behaviour. Notice that the database created on our local test design is maintained securely in a private registry designed for the E-commerce applications after implementing our method.

Table 4.1: Proposed model Buyer’s Evaluation Criteria.

User Types	Ranges
Buyer A to B	7 to 10
Buyer C to D	1 to 4
Buyer E to F	3 to 8
Buyer G to H	1 to 10
Buyer I to J	1 to 2 or 9 to 10

Table 4.2: Proposed model Seller’s Different Criteria.

User Types	Ranges
Seller for A	Fair
Seller for B	Poor
Seller for C	Balanced
Seller for D	Fair to Poor
Seller for E	Poor to Fair

In Table 4.1, we presented evaluation criteria for each buyer in eBay based on their given grades to eBay sellers with different ranges. Purchasers A and B are supportive consumers in the table who always provide 7 to 10 ranking grades. Buyers C and D, on the other hand, are stringent in the ranking, offering just 1 to 4. Buyers E, F, G, and H are casual consumers who compare purchases of narrower spans with an average of nearly to 5. Finally, buyers I and J rate between 1 to 2 or 9 to 10, who reflect exceptional circumstances such as shareholders, marketers, or those with definitive attributes that might occur in our everyday activities of E-commerce applications.

In addition, Table 4.2 displays 5 distinct virtual sellers representing various levels of suppliers. Particularly the overall ratings such as "fair to poor" and "poor to fair" sellers are required to predict their credibility changes all the time, based on the lower and upper such as decreased and growing ratings each acquire from prospective buyers. We generated 10 transactions for each purchaser-seller set, giving a total of 2,000 transactions. In other terms, each seller and buyers judged a hundred times and two hundred times, resulting in a total of four thousand transactions assessment.

Figure 4.7 and Figure 4.8 depicts the different rating scores for both categories of buyers such as supportive and strictly buyers, our proposed model utilises the cumulative average of rating scores and all four evaluation metrics such as PEC, T_{Ti} , S'_{Ra} , and MTree for both buyers categories. Figure 4.7 and Figure 4.8 show the normalisation process of the rating values based on their propensity from every user to provide grades for different sellers. Whenever it comes to supportive and stringent consumers, even if the actual ranking scores appear extraordinarily high or low, these are evenly distributed within the range of 0 and 10 after applying normalisation approach to all metrics. We evaluate the proposed model with a cumulative average of rating scores such as (Cum-Avg) and Personal Evaluation Criteria such as (PEC) metric only.

Figure 4.7: Normalized Evaluation for Supportive Buyers A to B.

Figure 4.7 depicts overall normalized evaluation distribution for buyers which are very supportive and s towards sellers on E-commerce applications, such as buyers A to B. Figure 4.7 shows that supportive buyers A to B achieve the Cum-Avg of 6 rating score for around initial 4 months, which suddenly rises to the Cum-Avg of 8 rating score after 8 months time period, then it again reaches to Cum-Avg of 6 rating score at 12 months. Similarly, supportive buyers PEC rating scores reach to the average of 8 rating score for initial 20 seconds time, which continues to 8 to 9

rating score after 4 months, then it again achieves the average of 9 rating score at month 10 to 12.

Figure 4.8: Normalized Evaluation for Strictly Buyers C to D.

Figure 4.8 depicts overall normalized evaluation values for buyers which are very strict with various E-commerce sellers, such as buyers C to D. Figure 4.8 shows that very strict buyers mainly C to D perceive the Cum-Avg of 4 rating score for around initial 20 seconds, which suddenly drops to the Cum-Avg of 2 rating score during first 3 months time period, then it again reaches to Cum-Avg of 4 rating score between month 9 to 12. Similarly, these strict buyers PEC rating scores stood at the average of 6 rating score for initial 3 months time, which continues to same rating score after 3 to 4 months time, then it slightly drops to the average of 5 rating score at last 2 months of a diagram.

However, it can be seen that supportive buyers such as A to B have higher Cum-Avg and PEC rating score as compared to strict buyers C to D.

Figure 4.9 and 4.10 represent the reputation of sellers such as "Fair to Poor" and "Poor to Fair" for seller D and Seller E respectively. Sellers trust score is evaluated based on four metrics such as PEC, MTree, T_{Ti} and S'_{Ra} , trust values and other ratings constantly changes over different time for seller D and seller E.

The trust score of sellers D such as "Fair to Poor" and seller E such as "Poor to Fair" is presented on rating scores between 0 to 10 scales over date.

Figure 4.9: Seller trust from Fair to Poor for Seller D.

Figure 4.9 depicts Seller D trust score in term of rating scores, which has received a trust score from "Fair to Poor".

From the figure, it can be seen that seller D trust score drastically increases from average 4 to 10 for first 9 months, after the end of month 9 seller D once again losses the trusts score, which gradually declines from average of 9 to average of 2 trust scores at month 10. After month 10 seller D overall trust scores decline to nearly 1 rating score level. This is due to fact that cumulative estimated value somehow doesn't follow certain guidelines based on normalised tendency and later appears to fall behind due to the massive amount of out-dated transactions history.

Figure 4.10 depicts Seller E trust score in term of rating scores, which has received trust score from "Poor to Fair" From the figure we can observe that seller E trust score exponentially increases from 2 to 5 between month 4 to 9, after month 9 seller E losses the trusts score for an average of 4 rating score.

Then after month 10, seller E again gains a good trust score, which significantly

Figure 4.10: Seller trust from Poor to Fair for Seller E

increases 5 rating scores to nearly 10 rating scores. This is due to fact that cumulative estimated value somehow utilises certain guidelines for normalised tendency and due to less number of transaction records.

4.5 Discussion and use cases

At different granularities, the transaction context can be described. Suppose a customer wants to buy "Canon Wide Angle Glasses" from a retailer. His/her query with transaction contexts can be \langle product-category: , time-range: $[T_{TiMin}]$, $[T_{TiMax}]$, overall rating: \rangle . $[T_{TiMin}]$ refers to the starting time of the buyer query and $[T_{TiMax}]$ is the last time which is within 6 months (e.g.) the buyer wants to know if the seller is trustworthy in selling Canon Wide Angle Lenses in the last twelve months while the seller's overall rating is 91%. As a result, the buyer's query would be \langle product-category: Wide Angle Lenses, time-range: from present to 6 months ago, overall rating: 91% \rangle . Following the proposed method, The seller's tree needs to be created in order to easily follow his/her selling behaviour history. Figure 4.11 shows an example of the seller tree which has some transactions made.

Figure 4.11: An example of the seller’s history

Example 1: Assume a seller can make a new deal by selling "Canon EF 75-300mm f/4-5.6 III Wide Angle lens". As depicted in Figure 4.11, the seller’s transactions tree has 713 transactions in selling Canon Wide Angel lens. The newest transaction made in the category was 15 days ago and the oldest transaction made in the same category was 250 days ago and the overall rating of the seller is 91%. As a result, the buyer’s query should be <product-category: Canon EF 75-300mm f/4-5.6 III Wide Angle lens, time-range: from present to 6 months ago, overall rating: 91 %>. Based on the proposed approach, the vender easily sold the same item between the $[T_{TiMin}]$ (Now) and $[T_{TiMax}]$. Therefore, the similarity between the new transaction and the last transactions is 'ONE' as the seller received a good transactions trust in selling the product. After considering the transaction time dimension in the final trust value equation as discussed in the equation 4.1, the final trust of the seller in selling Canon EF 75-300mm f/4-5.6 III Wide Angle lens" is stood at 0.95, which is a significant and acceptable level, provided in Table 4.3, as he has a good history in selling this product and has a good overall rating.

Example 2: Suppose a vendor makes a new sale by selling "Sony Alpha NEX-5 Big Angels Lens." As shown in Figure 4.11, the seller's transactions tree has no transaction made in selling any Sony Alpha Wide Angel lens but he/she has already sold some products similar to this category such as Canon Wide Angel lens and Nikon Wide Angle Lens. The newest transaction made in the same category was 2 days ago and the oldest transaction made in the same category was 250 days ago and the overall rating of the seller is 91%. As a result, the buyer's query should be <product-category: Sony Alpha NEX-5 Wide Angels Lens, time-range: from present to 6 months ago, overall rating: 91%>. Following the proposed method, the seller has sold the same product between the $[T_{TiMin}]$ (Now) and $[T_{TiMax}]$. Moreover, the similarity co-relation between the new transaction of an item and the last transactions of an item can be achieved less than 'ONE' due to fact that the seller has a limited experience to sell such product, so the penalty 'P' is determined in this case, which is trust attribute. As a result, $P = 1 - SIM_{level}$ which is 0.04 so the similarity between the new transaction and the last transaction after applying 'P' is 0.96. After considering the transaction time dimension in the final trust value equation 4.1 as discussed in last section the final trust of the seller in selling "Sony Alpha NEX-5 Wide Angels Lens" stood at 0.93, which is also acceptable and significant level as depicted in the Table 4.3. as he/she has a good history in selling another product in the same category and has a good overall rating.

Example 3: Suppose a seller will do a new transaction by selling "Nikon AF-S DX 18-300 mm f/3.5-6.3 G ED VR Lens." As shown in Figure 4.11 the seller's transactions tree has 831 transactions made in selling Nikon Wide Angle lens. The newest transaction made in the same category was 197 days ago and the last transaction made in the same category was 258 days ago and the overall rating of the seller is 91%. As a result, the buyer's query should be <product-category: Sony Alpha NEX-5 Wide Angels Lens, time-range: from present to 6 months ago, overall rating: 91%>. The seller has not sold the same product within the $[T_{TiMin}]$ (Now)

and $[T_{TiMax}]$ (180 days). However, the last transaction has been made was before $[T_{TiMax}]$ (180 days). Overall, in this case, the proposed method depicts that “Upper Range (UR)” which is achieved at 10% of the 180 days (6 months). Following the proposed method, the similarity between the new transaction and the last transactions is recorded around 0.94 as the seller has not sold the same product between the present and upper range of 6 months which is 198 days which means he/she is not selling in the same time range of the same product. After considering the transaction time dimension in the final trust value equation as discussed in last section the final trust of the seller in selling “Nikon AF-S DX 18-300mm f/3.5-6.3 G ED VR Lens+ Wide Angel lens” is 0.92, which is acceptable and feasible level in the trust-based model as shown in Table 4.3, as he/she has a good history in selling this product and has a good overall rating. The section shows some examples of how the proposed method can be used in different scenarios in order to evaluate the trustworthiness within the online transaction using two dimensions Transaction Time Dimension (T_{Ti}) and overall rating Dimension (S'_{Ra}). This scenario has been demonstrated to show how this method enables to lower down the value imbalance problem which is can happen if the seller changes his/her behaviour in selling expensive products after building a good trust by selling cheap products. These values are calculated by the buyers after each created transaction on the basis of the values given. These values are usually a number set such as the eBay rating scores, which are [-1,0,1]. While Epinions shows the scores as an integer [0,1,2,3,4,5]. According to the authors of [75], to evaluate trust value by using the numerical values that are in 0,1 are considered as significant values. Therefore, the final trust value was categorised in five scales as shown in the Table 4.3.

Table 4.3: Rating Scores Categorizations

Poor	Medium	Good	Excellent
$0 \leq T < 0.25$	$0.25 \leq T < 0.5$	$0.5 \leq T < 0.75$	$0.75 \leq T \leq 1$

4.6 Summary

In this chapter, we suggested an effective way to extract reputation and trust from raw reviews contained in online transaction transactions. To make values further stable, consistent and realistic, several concepts and principles relevant to human behaviour, Personal Evaluation Criteria (PEC), and other variables, such as MTree, S'_{Ra} , T_{Ti} have been applied to calculate similarities and difference for time gap and weight. Our proposed approach is called a contextual trust evaluation method because some transaction contexts such as transaction time and value imbalance. This approach will help to avoid the imbalance problem by calculating the similarity between the two measurements. This method suggests that the trust value of any seller needs to be decreased if he/she changes the behaviour in order to prevent cheating by selling expensive products after gaining a good reputation by selling cheap products. .

Chapter 5

Estimating Multi-Dimensional Trust From E-commerce Consumers Feedback Comments

5.1 Introduction

There is a great relationship between the success of any E-commerce system or website and an accurate trust evaluation mechanism. According to [110] there are many trust and reputation reporting mechanisms that have been adapted in different E-commerce websites such as Amazon and eBay, where sellers trust and reputation score are calculated with the help of calculating aggregated feedback ratings. In eBay, the values of trust and reputation are considered as aggregated percentage values for the positive ratings evaluated from the overall positive and negative rating values, these values are evaluated for around the last 12 months transactions. According to [110], [111] the main issue of the trust and reputation reporting system of eBay is “ALL GOOD REPUTATION” problem which means that the majority of feedback ratings are 99% and over as positive ratings. Therefore, this kind of

mechanism does not consider any changes in a seller's behaviour which can lead the frauds to be committed. There is a noticeable lack of the buyers' reviews and one of the possible reasons for that is the buyer who writes a negative rating might negatively affect his/her own trust [110]. On the other hand, the buyers who write a positive feedback, they include some disappointing expressions alongside with their positive feedback for example, "the item is as shown in the photos" or "as expected" which mean positive feedback towards the item while whereas the mention "Slow delivery" is negative feedback toward the service. Therefore, there is a great demand to analyze the provided information in the buyers' feedback comments in order to detect their opinions about different properties of the transactions and then computing the comprehensive trust and reputation value for any sellers. In this chapter, we propose an approach that can automatically weight the dimensions of concerns and in our proposed approach, we have mainly focused on the sold products frequency, and dimensions of different products sold, the transaction amount dimension, the transaction time dimension and the overall ratings of seller dimension. Our proposed model is extended to include the factor based on the feedback mining and extraction in E-commerce application such as eBay and Amazon.

In this chapter, we suggest a framework that integrates dependency relationship evaluation [27], [26], this method is created with the collaboration of lexical opinions based data mining [146], [79], and Natural Language Processing (NLP), which can be used to mine or extract the given feedback aspect expressions for the purpose of classifying opinions. Addition to this, we have also utilised an algorithm, which enables to evaluate based on the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) also known as topic modelling technique [13] and correlation analysis technique, this algorithm provides feasible support for to aggregating feature sequences as dimensions. Apart from standard topic modelling [13], [53] of uni-gram interpretations for textual information our classification is based on the dependence relationship interpretations of aspect expression of opinions. Moreover, we also comprise the use of the frame-

works in terms of aspect and opinion, and also the antecedent established by the relationship of dependency, in terms of achieving more efficient clustering.

Finally, predefined dimensions (e.g. products types dimension, the number of the products sold dimension and the transactions amounts dimension, the transactions times dimension and the overall ratings dimension) can be weighted simply by aggregating the percentage of the clusters that contain these dimensions overall the total percentage of the clusters of concerns.

5.2 Multi-Dimensional Trust Factors based on E-commerce Feedback Comments

Table 1

Examples of Buyers' Review on Amazon

No	comment	Rating
C1	good product, expensive, friendly seller	1
C2	highly recommended seller	1
C3	bad quality, won't buy again	1
C4	slow delivery, good item	1
C5	good price, great seller	1
C6	friendly seller, slow postage	1
C7	not as expected	1
C8	delivered on time, quick response	1

In our research, we manipulate and analyse the provided users feedback comments, which they provide as overall opinion during purchasing order or after each transaction. It is clear after the analysis of the feedback on Amazon that is the buyers leave mixed opinions about different transaction aspects even if they leave positive expressions for the whole transaction. Table 1 shows some examples which are ran-

domly taken from Amazon reviews with the ratings of Amazon. For example, C1 is a positive review rating for the transaction but the buyer left a negative impression about another aspect in the comment “good product”, “expensive”, “friendly seller”. It is clear that the buyer he/she was not satisfied with the price although he/she leave as supportive feedback also known as a positive score for the whole transaction. However, the user’s feedback comments comprise different contexts of the transaction (e.g. quality, transaction time and overall rating). Therefore, the proposed method considers all these different aspects of every comment in order to weight the transaction contexts (dimensions).

Definition 3.1. *The cumulative trust score for a seller is T_{final} , which is comprised of the vendor’s overall aggregated trust-based dimensional weight score. The cumulative trust score for a seller is T_{final} provided with the following equation:*

$$\sum_{D=1}^{D=n} (T^D \times W^D) \quad (5.1)$$

In which T^D depicts the weighted trust scores and W^D represents the weighted dimensions accordingly.

5.3 Evaluation of Dimensional Weights for Feedback Comments

Firstly our model mainly focused on the typed dependency analysis to extracting aspect opinion expressions then, we introduce our LDA-based segmentation algorithm for clustering dimension phrases and weights of computational parameters.

5.3.1 Extracting Aspect Expressions by Typed Dependency Analysis

A NLP method from Stanford to explain precisely the grammatical associations in phrases is the typed dependency relation representation [27]. A term is defined as a series of different relationships for words and phrases in the context of (head, dependent) with typed dependency relationship parsing, where content words are selected as heads, and other corresponding words rely on the heads.

Our research is focused on LDA algorithm, an algorithm for extracting input on measurement weights, integrating natural language processing methods, information extraction, and subject/topic modelling is created to evaluate Amazon data sets such as (Rating, Product Type, Price, Time interval, and Quantity Sold). Based on the correlation of overall ratings, their feature ratings and weights are evaluated but significant positive bias is not reflected in the overall ratings.

For example, parsing the comment *nice reader. almost perfect for what I want/need. good bargain* using widely used Stanford typed dependency parser. The comments acquired from feedback includes three phrases: *Nice reader(reader, nice)*. The expression does not rely on every other term, then it is set as the root level. *Almost perfect for what I want/need* and *Good bargain*. The sentence *Good bargain* also can be represented as (head, dependent) and (*bargain, good*).

Some dependency relations will be selected to ensure that the comment expresses opinion towards dimensions. It has been stated in [142] that expressions generated with the help of lexical subjective elements including nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs. We choose the interactions that represent the changing relation between adjectives or nouns, and adverbs or verbs, as defined by the translator of the significant positive relationship, among the interactions representing grammatical connections. These shifting relationships as seen in Table 2. It has been shown that

5.3. EVALUATION OF DIMENSIONAL WEIGHTS FOR FEEDBACK COMMENTS

Table 2

Co-relation for Typed-Dependencies	Feedback-Examples
Modifier for Adjective $Adj-mod(N_N, J_J)$	<i>Nice reader</i>
Modifier for Adverbs $Adv-mod(V_B, R_B)$	<i>Rapid shipment</i>
Modifier for Nominal subject $N-sub(J_J, N_N)$	<i>Item was excellent</i>
Complement for adjectives $comp(VB, JJ)$	<i>Very Quick delivered</i>

the noun or verb normally reflects the target concept under discussion with the varying relationships, while the adjective or adverb reflects a view on the target word. Therefore, the changing partnerships may be referred to as(modifier, head)pairs. The Modifier for Adjective $Adj-mod(N_N, J_J)$ and Modifier for Nominal subject $N-sub(J_J, N_N)$ relationships of dependence signify the pairs (modifier, head), namely (super, shipping) and (excellent, product). Designers call such representations of (modifier, head) pair dimensions.

5.3.2 Dimension Expressions Clustering

The technique of Lexical-LDA is widely used as a group of various expressions of parameters into grammatically consistent groups that we consider dimensions. LDA based on lexical pattern enables to utilise the superficial learning strategies of topic modelling dependency relationships to accomplish more efficient clustering, unlike the traditional topic model structure, which requires the text by term matrix as input. The clustering problem can be described under the subject modelling in collaboration with the superficial lexical information, acquired as dependency-based interaction specification towards dimensional expressions, provided as below: A redistribution of topics also initiates the dimensional expression as phrases, which are related to the same modifiers term or negation of a modifier expression, so that a unique topic modelling is triggered in turn by an exchange of head phrases.

This methodology enables everyone to utilise such organised dependent relationship specifications for clustering from the constraint relationship parser. Lexical-LDA

inputs feedback in the context of (modifier-term, head-term) is also considered as pairs or respective negations, such as (good, bargain) or (not-good, seller) dependence relationships for dimension expressions.

Suppose, we considered T , K and R as populations numbers, the number of subjects and the number of phrase symbols in the language, respectively.

Also we considered hyper-parameters for the proportions exchanging on topics and on the mixing elements of topics be α and β , respectively. Equation 5.2 below [161] is a notification equation to evaluate the full probability mean of the pi word token for the S topic, where $i = (a, b)$ denotes the n^{th} word term in the given the a^{th} document type, where as $p = \{pi = t, p-i\}$, $q = \{qi = S, q-i\}$ and $n(\cdot), -i$ depicts the counting iteration, i is exempted and hyper-parameters are also exempted from the corresponding document or subject.

$$p \times [(q_i = S|q-i, p)] \times (\alpha) = \frac{(n_{S,-i}^{(t)} + \beta_t)}{\sum_{t=1}^V (n_{S,-i}^{(t)} + \beta_t)} \times \frac{(b_{a,-i}^{(S)} + \alpha_S)}{\sum_{S=1}^{S=n} (b_{a,-i}^{(S)} + \alpha_S)} \quad (5.2)$$

The proposed LDA algorithm enables to change and modifies the previous distribution with the help of weighted factors, to create and allocate new dimensions for head terms, these allocations are used for modifier phases in words, the second form of lexical information that implies usually two head terms from the same statement is used for various definition and approaches. In general, for the heading phrase pi with indexed $i = (a, b)$, when computing the probabilities of $p \times [(qi = S-i]$, we characterise the proof as given by the heading contexts in the same original comment as wi when computing the probability distribution of $p \times [(qi = k-i]$, head terms in the same statement with wi and is directly linked with a subject other than S needs to cast an advantageous vote f while calculating the probability distribution of $p \times [(q_i = S|q-i]$.

$$f(q_i = S) = \frac{(b_{a,-i}^{(Cs,-S)}) - b_{(a,-i)}^{(Cs,S)}}{b_{a,-i}^{(Cs)}} \quad (5.3)$$

In which Cs indicates the series of comments that wi looks likely, $n(Cs, -S)a, -i$ represents the m head terms count apart from pi that makes it appear in any Cs statement and is allotted to a topic apart from S , $n(Cs, k)a, -i$ hypothetical questions the a head terms count other than pi that appears in any Cs statement and is allocated to the S topic, and $n(c)m, -i$ indicates the m head level elements count other than wi that also seems in any Cs statement and is allocated to the S topic, and $n(Cs)a, -i$ indicates the a head definitions number. The result is $f(q_i = S) \in [-1, 1]$.

$$\begin{cases} if > 0 & \text{consider more positive selection,} \\ if = 0 & \text{consider same number from positive or same negative selection,} \\ if < 0 & \text{consider more negative selection} \end{cases}$$

In Equation 5.3 [164], our proposed approach introduce the weights to change the cumulative likelihood calculation. Since the pi head terms with the $i = (a, b)$ index is the n^{th} head term for the a modifiers term, whether the head terms occur in the similar statement like pi , given in Equation 5.4 as below:

$$p \times [(q_i = S | q_{-i}, p)] \times (\alpha) = (1 + \alpha * f(q_i = kS)) \cdot \frac{n_{S,-i}^{(t)} + \beta_t}{\sum_{t=1}^V (n_{S,-i}^{(t)} + \beta_t)} \cdot \frac{b_{a,-i}^{(S)} + \alpha_S}{\sum_{S=1}^S (b_{a,-i}^{(S)} + \alpha_S)} \quad (5.4)$$

When implementing Equation 5.4, all three components given below need to be

differentiated.

- If $f(qi = S) > 0$, such that, in the same statements, there are many more headwords that justify applying pi to S , the probability density calculation is improved by sampler.

If $f(qi = S) < 0$, which indicates that there are more headwords occurred in the same comment, which are opposed to pi being applied to the subject S , the sampler's conditional likelihood calculation is reduced.

- Otherwise, $f(qi = S) = 0$ retains the initial calculation of the sampling.

In Equation 5.4, the parameter $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ represents the degree of information power represented in $f(qi = S)$. The explanation is that such information is predictive in this nature. The ranges of $(1 - \alpha)$, $(1 + \alpha)$ for the modification element such as $(1 + \alpha - f(qi = S))$ is also used. Remember that for all discussions afterwards, the modified likelihood determined by Equation 5.4 will be normalised. The structure for modification such as (modifier or head) components are first investigated in the research of [82] for topic modelling evaluation. Probabilistic Latent Semantic Analysis (PLSA) is also used in [82] where the several weighted dimensions are merged together to evaluate the for the dimensional concept, where EM is mainly used for optimisation.

The LDA pattern is often used in our solution. More specifically, to create more meaningful clusters, we add further lexical information to restrict the method of grouping headwords. We calculate different weights score for quantities including modifier term, head-term pairs, addition to this our model also feasibly classifies and grouped negation based quantities within the same group. The weighted values evaluated for such a pair of a variable is intuitively considered equivalent to the aggregated number of positive and negative for these dimensions. In fact, for the dimensional, we determine the total number of (modifier-term or head-term

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dimensional pairs. Indeed, only recurrent dimensional phrases are included with headwords, where our model only achieve the 0.1% of reviews that occur in at least 0.1% of reviews. To generate the dimensional weights and the overall number of dimensional expressions quantities after the normalisation process.

We found that our dataset of dimensions and opinions was divided into 70 topics that represent the customers' dimensions into their comments. Finally, to weight the factors that we assume that the seller trust relies on, we need to interpret the keywords of the topic. Table 3 shows some examples of topic keywords and percentage then we select the topics that represent our factors then calculate each factor weight as follows:

$$F_w = \frac{1}{C} \sum_{i=0}^n c_i \quad (5.5)$$

where c_i denote the topic percentage that represents one from our five factors (e.g. price, rate, product type, time interval and quantity sold) and C denotes the total percentage of topics that represent one of our factors.

Table 3

TopicID	Percentage	Keywords
0	0.0295	great product, perfect size
1	0.0092	great quality, excellent quality
2	0.4175	great tablet, really enjoy
3	0.023	highly recommend, much fun
4	0.0062	cheap tablet, excellent price

5.4 Dataset

This work is based on costumers' reviews of Amazon which is 34.000 reviews which is about Amazon products including Amazon Alexa, the kindle, FireTV Stick and much more. This dataset includes basic product information, rating, and review.txt for each product. In our proposed research main data was collected from real-time data repository such Amazon sellers.

5.5 Results

Reputation management systems of popular e-commerce websites like eBay and Amazon suffer from problems like “all good reputation”. The high reputation scores for sellers can not effectively rank sellers and therefore can not guide potential buyers to select trustworthy sellers to transact with. Designing a solution for the “All good reputation” to evaluates seller trust needs two steps. First, assume factors that the seller trust relies on and in this paper, we assume they are (price, rating, product type, quantity sold and time interval). Finally, we can't give all factors the same weight into our trust calculation equation so we used topic modeling, typed dependency parsing and NLP techniques to estimate each factor weight and finally we got the following:

1. $Rating = 0.646$

2. $Product - type = 0.176$

3. $Price = 0.083$

4. *Time – interval* = 0.073

5. *Quantity – sold* = 0.022

5.6 Summary

Popular E-commerce platforms such as eBay and Amazon’s trust management practices suffer from the effects like ”all great record.” The high seller credibility scores do not efficiently rate several vendors, which also lead as prospective buyers should not be instructed to select trustworthy vendors from whom to buy. Designing a solution for the “All good reputation” to evaluates seller trust needs two steps. First, assume factors that the seller trust relies on and in this paper, we assume they are (price, rating, product type, quantity sold and time interval). Finally, we can’t give all factors the same weight into our trust calculation equation so we used topic modelling, typed dependency parsing and NLP techniques to estimate each factor weight and finally we got the following:

Chapter 6

Role of Machine Learning and Blockchain Security Framework for Distributed E-Commerce in SDN context

6.1 Introduction

In recent years, E-commerce, along with economic globalisation and the advancement of the Internet, has seen its dramatic growth. E-commerce exchange and distribution require partnerships amongst E-commerce supply chain participants. Developing trust among supply chain participants has become a crucial problem [70]. Because of the variations between countries in culture, legislation, and philosophy [129], the issue of trust could not be easily rectified. As our research is based on creating feasible trust between E-commerce sellers and buyers, also our proposed research enables trust between sellers and buyers during their active interaction and online trust formation process. There have been a lot of existing work already pub-

lished to build trust for E-commerce applications, but many researchers have failed to explore the dilemma in a multifaceted and multidimensional manner for trust models. Previous chapters help to create trust by measuring the similarity between the new transaction and the past transactions in the product types dimension, the number of the products sold dimension, and the transactions amount dimension. Similarly, our other contribution provides trust for E-commerce sellers and buyers with the help of estimating the similarities between the new transactions of a purchaser and the previous sales record of a buyer. In addition to this, another contribution is based on mining customers comments and feedback expressed in free text

In this final chapter, the model is designed in collaboration with the Software-Defined Networking (SDN) and blockchain. SDN allows versatile implementation and advancement of modern networking applications due to the programmability approach, and decoupling of the control plane from the data plane, the concept and way of developing and operating interconnected networks has evolved dramatically and reduced the obstacles in the e-commerce markets. Our model provides trust and effective security with medium CPU and memory overhead, which can help E-commerce applications to exponentially grow in the current market. Blockchain-based SDN has become an evolving architecture to protect a distributed network framework with the introduction of blockchain applications. In this model, the major objective of our research is to optimize the security between various E-commerce applications/businesses, also to mitigate the single point failure of security vulnerabilities via Blockchain-based SDN framework. Our proposed model also utilises the trust between E-commerce applications with the help of blockchain-based trust key distribution.

The implementation of Blockchain technologies provides several new thoughts on the administration of the E-commerce supply chain [32]. Within the sense of cross-border E-commerce, participants' credit measurement is their most significant bar-

rier to achieving a deal [22]. Blockchain's fundamental importance is the development of open and straightforward algorithm based laws, and the creation of a trusted network, maintaining business confidentiality and gaining identity legitimacy in dynamic environments [133].

The latest E-commerce platform implementation contains its vast amounts of data relating to customers, goods, and distributors. The data collection, maintenance, and examination methods have grown significantly. The E-commerce network has the inherent benefit of integrating data from upstream producers or vendors, middle network operators, and downstream customers [162]. The incorporation of Blockchain and E-commerce development also provides a variety of unanswered questions. Accomplishing verification of product details in a Blockchain-based structure demands for a modern framework architecture, involving technical expertise on E-commerce management for the supply chain. The larger amount of data produced from E-commerce in the Blockchain demands a more effective model of architecture. Also, it is very essential to address the protection related concerns inside the Blockchain-based shared communication protocol. New algorithms for information protection and key control approaches should be built to secure data protection within E-commerce applications.

This study addresses some of these limitations by implementing a Blockchain-based system and presenting a group of related frameworks, strategies, and algorithms, this study addresses the aforementioned limitations. The conceptual architecture, which focuses on the issue of trust between E-commerce applications also to classify the severe attacks inside such a network.

Most of the existing approaches for trust-based E-commerce communication and attacks detection in SDN are limited due to such challenges as below:

- Centralization: Many attack vector identification techniques rely on a centralized paradigm, in which an attacker is classified by a centralized cloud server

using a centralized intrusion detection system. Because the whole system combines a large number of users, these techniques are challenging to scale. Furthermore, due to capacity problems, high processing speeds, high latency, and single-point loss, the central cloud would remain unstable.

- Big data problem:

Identification of security threats is a significant data challenge due to the large quantity of data that must be acquired from communication equipment and the system for real-time data processing. Many real-time data sources provide a specialized decision to identify activities. However, collecting and processing real-time data in E-commerce systems would be prohibitively expensive. Furthermore, by inserting harmful inaccurate information, such as bandwidth usage and redundancy [106], these difficulties appear to restrict the precision of threat categorization in E-commerce apps in this study.

- Lack of privacy: The most recent techniques for identifying threats do not prioritize data security. They process data in a variety of ways without the owner's permission. Furthermore, owing to the issue of user privacy, existing methods of detecting assaults are unable to collect enough data, resulting in erroneous identification estimates. [105].

6.2 Proposed Methods and Functions for E-commerce Applications

6.2.1 Design Overview

Figure 6.1 provides a conceptual summary of our proposed model, which is designed with the three-layered paradigm consist of the following layers:

- Layer-1 comprises various E-commerce applications based on their sellers and consumers of products. Distributed relationship of each seller and their trustworthy buyers are protected with the help of Blockchains trust communications. This is implemented with Ethereum Blockchain technology to provide trust communication between E-commerce applications, which also helps to identify the attacks effectively.
- Layer-2 is implemented with a centralized SDN POX controller, to configure and update Ethereum nodes remotely, also continuously monitor and analyse of traffic data with TCPDUMP and Mininet. The second stage comprises faster, reliable and more efficient SDN. Each SDN switch on the second level is linked to many separate hosts on its premises, which are actively used for collecting and monitoring layer 1 incoming traffic. All traffic from layer-1 and layer-2 is transformed toward the layer-3.
- layer-3 is created based on deep machine learning classifier such as gradient descent algorithm to classify attacks non-attacks and trust and distrust in E-commerce applications following by SDN collected data. In addition, each SDN controller reports the results to its related layer 3 ML-based classifications for the surveillance of anomalous execution and evaluation on a substantial and long-term basis.

The proposed model, layer-2, SDN control plane is the combination of two layers as data flow analyser, Blockchain-based trust and attack detection. The first component is mainly focusing to collect and analyse the malicious and normal data. The second component enables to provide the trust also to identify the anomalous activity for E-commerce applications.

As SDN has developed as the most feasible programmable network architecture for addressing various issues in older infrastructures. For dealing with Denial of Service (DoS) and Distributed DoS (DDoS) assaults, and evaluation of trust automatically

Figure 6.1: Blockchain based E-commerce Trust Model in SDN

and effectively. SDN management systems become the most interesting objects to utilise any customized applications in collaboration with blockchain and machine learning.

In our proposed chapters such as chapters 3,4 and 5 our proposed models were not focusing on integrity and controllability of adaptive trust calculation without human interaction. In this Chapter 6, SDN enables us to evaluate trust with enhanced controllability and integrity of trust evaluation, it also proved security and privacy.

6.2.2 Data flow analyser

The traffic flow analyser tracks network traffic from several E-commerce applications continuously and records data characteristics, such as the traffic packets and flow levels, including the performance of the system at specific intervals, the use of bandwidth, a cumulative amount of service requests from a system, source of demand and so on. During normal data checks, recorded datasets are classified as normal, which will be used for training purpose in the ML model to classify the attacks. In addition, the data flow analyser often includes numerous identified E-commerce applications flaws, some documented threat patterns (e.g. DDoS, TCP flooding), and target Domain names mentioned in blacklist to classify the attacks in the E-commerce applications. The traffic flow analyser thus receives information about malicious and legitimate traffic and delivers that information to the ML classifiers to evaluate the results.

6.3 Trust between E-commerce Applications

Most of the symmetric encryption algorithm, like Ellipse Curve Cryptography (ECC) [41], Diffie-Hellman [108], and RSA [154] are significantly considered as

safeguard provider for data transmission against threats whilst retaining users with scalable access in the Blockchain-based E-commerce applications. Such algorithms also solve discrete logarithm issues, that are hard to crack the keys the security keys produced by RSA. RSA framework allocates the shared key which can accommodate a wide variety of users' key operational issues, but a key for each operation is challenging to produce. The ECC is similar to RSA with better protection efficiency, quicker processing power and reduced storage space.

If the ECC algorithm key is too small, therefore the degree of protection could not be assured properly. Within an unstable network environment, the Diffie-Hellman algorithm can compromise keys but cannot avoid scammer attempts. For DSA's electronic signatures and verification, the applicant registers file or confirmation using its own private key and the receiver utilizes the sender's public key to verify authentication legitimacy after obtaining the notification. DSA is just a type of digital authentication that is different from RSA. It can not be validated or authenticated, but its verification frequency is higher even than RSA. In the light of the requirements of the various entities involved in E-commerce, their legitimacy could be categorized as follows: buyers and sellers account, item transactions, supervision and enforcement. The stored information in a block cannot be modified or corrupted within the Blockchain network. The modification of data by keys with access and upgrade permissions should be reviewed to avoid incompatible records being created. The tree structure is used for transaction handling keys. Various keys are utilised for the different purposes of security, whereas the parent key holds all the privileges of all its items.

Our proposed model is based on elliptical encryption digital signature algorithm (ECDSA) [7], [17], [72] and [155]. In this model, encryption algorithm is based on elliptical encryption digital signature algorithm (ECDSA) [7], [17], [72] and [155], where elliptical encryption algorithm is utilised via SECP256kl [148]. Key distribution is also used with the collaboration of BIP0039 protocol [100], which is

based on hierarchical deterministic wallet BIP0039 protocol.

6.3.1 Trust Key Distribution

The keys are allocated according to a tree structure during the key distribution process as depicted in Figure 6.2, where the parent keys comprise stronger power and influence over their own descendant keys. The individual's initial public key strategy [81] is provided as below in Equation 6.1,

$$(P_K, P_k) \Rightarrow (C_K^i, C_k^i) = i = 1, 2, 3, \dots n \quad (6.1)$$

Where P values denote the parent key, C values denote next value, which is also managed and generated by P like $P \in C$.

In Figure 6.2, a detailed method of the key generation process is provided for each of the trust entities.

Based on Equation 6.1 and Figure 6.2 on page 119, a detailed method of the key generation process is provided for each of the trust entities. The individual's initial public key is created with the help of BIP-0039 protocol, SHA and CSPRN-Gen(N).

1. Based on the protocol of BIP-0039, as trust communication, we have utilised the random order of 128 bits entropy estimation such as (E), where we consider the degree of randomness sequences via generating the cryptographically secure pseudorandom numbers such as CSPRN-Gen(N), where $N = 1.56 \times 10^{77}$, this provides feasible support to distribute trust factor.
2. With the help of SHA-256 hashing function, we extracted the first four bits for purpose of applying random sequence checksum such as (check-sum), here check-sum value is set as SHA-256 (E, 4).

3. All the values of check-sum are stored in random sequence order, then classified into different sequences of 11 subsets, which is provided as below:

$$Set(i) = \frac{check - sum}{E}, i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 11 \quad (6.2)$$

4. After manipulation check-sum, these values are utilised to as seed values in order to create private key with pull key function of PBKDF-2, proposed by [65], which enables to create 512-bit seed (feature list). Value of 512-bit seed is used to calculate the following values:

$$PBKDF(2) = Match \Rightarrow (Set_i) \times (Feat), i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 11 \quad (6.3)$$

5. In Equation 6.4 Seed values are used as input to HMAC via SHA-512 bits algorithm to create private key for all entities of E-commerce. Master key is derived based on the calculation and manipulation of individual private keys such as (IK), which poses initial key values. Also, master chain code Mcc_{val} is utilised for the purpose of next available key level, values of IK and Mcc_{val} are calculated as below:

$$Mcc_{val} \Rightarrow (HMAC - SHA512) \times (seed), \frac{512}{2} = 256 \quad (6.4)$$

6.3.2 Trust Function Key Distribution

In ECC algorithm based key distribution mechanism, we utilise the trust aware based secure and more reliable model with the help of between E-commerce applications nodes. The function key distribution is mainly focusing upon the initial key distribution approach. Combined distribution of initial and function keys enables to provides the feasible trust and authenticity of various functions and attributes. Key generation mechanism is provided in Figure 6.3.

Figure 6.2: Trust Key Distribution

The degree of higher trust or authority must be special among organizations and authorities. The initial key is often utilised to create the secondary key. The function keys are normally generated with the help of utilising secondary key distribution, which is coupled with the given function or authorization level. The key generation method to provide trust [50] is given as below:

Stage - 1 Public keys are calculated from users initial keys by utilising the ECC algorithm followed by $IK = Ik_G$.

Stage - 2 Our model also merges the public key values such as (IK) and master chain code Mcc_{val} values, where index values such as (n) helps to calculate the secondary key such as (Sk). Function of index distribution is provided as below:

$$Mcc_{val} \Rightarrow (HMAC - SHA512)IK \Phi Mcc_{val} + n \frac{512}{2} = 256 \quad (6.5)$$

Stage - 3 Mechanism of function key distribution offers multi-level key management, which effectively distributes the keys to implement a trustworthy interrelationship, which is given as $IK = Ik_G$.

$$F_{key} \Rightarrow (HMAC - SHA512)SK \Phi Mcc_{val} + F_{level} \frac{512}{2} = 256 \quad (6.6)$$

Figure 6.3: Trust Function Key Distribution

6.4 Data Processing and Manipulation

In our model, traffic collection and attack detection or mitigation of E-commerce applications are mainly focused on SDN based layer-2 and layer 3 ML-based classification for anomalous traffic from normal. SDN based layer-2 plays a very important role for traffic collection and policies insertion to all other layers, such as with the help of Pox SDN controller, we update the blockchain rules towards the first layer, which helps to effectively provide trust between all nodes and also support to classify the attacks in SDN switches. Our SDN based novel approach is described in Figure 6.1.

The proposed approach for traffic collection and manipulation from E-commerce applications comprises on two main entities such as SDN controller and trust agents, SDN controller is responsible for managing blockchain-based trust relationship between all primary layer, also to maintain and configure the detection layer of the model. SDN controller utilises the various data-driven tasks such as collecting and managing input data, creating and managing output data for attack detection model in layer 3. As seen in Figure1, the central layer is used as the central control layer, which feasibly delivers the testing data set towards to the attack detection model for classifying such data with the help of ML classifiers. Testing data set is created

on the basis of input data, which was collected from the first layer of E-commerce applications. Overall, central layer feasibly plays various tasks for data collection and rules insertion based on programmability and decoupling approach of Pox SDN controller. On the other hand, trust agents are also used between E-commerce nodes with the help of blockchain-based trust key distribution and trust function keys distribution by using unique public and private keys of the ECC algorithm. These agents effectively provide trust mechanism and make all nodes more secure and trustworthy, also these agents help to collect input data set from various sellers and buyers E-commerce activities over the internet. These trust aware agents are responsible to verify and authenticate the collected datasets for ML-based attack detection model. All entities involved in the SDN controller and trust agents are directly connected with the help of the ECC algorithm, which is implemented with the help of Ethereum approach.

In our proposed approach, we deployed Ethereum and ECC with the help of truffle development [153], Web3.js API, and Oraclize API [105] have also been used for the purpose of development. The development tool suite is created with Intel Xeon E5 CPU with 16GB RAM on Ubuntu 18.02 version. POX SDN controller is also deployed as the main controller of our proposed model. Two main actions are performed in the proposed model as depicted in Figure 6.4. The first action such as the SDN controller initiate trust between entities and collect datasets for data-driven tasks, including input data structure, data processing, and managing output data for attack detection model in layer 3. Data-driven tasks are manipulated with the help of agents, which provide support to cater to a reliable trust mechanism and make all nodes more secure and trustworthy. In addition to this, agents help to collect input data set from various sellers and buyers of E-commerce activities over the internet. These trust aware agents are responsible to verify and authenticate the collected datasets for ML-based attack detection model on local data sets. Our model utilises the InterPlanetary File System (IPFS) approach to

recording all input data as a database [10], IPFS enables to store feasible parameters for detection model acquired from E-commerce application nodes via hash values of ECC algorithm. IPFS hash values are then transferred to layer-3, to process the detection model in ML-based classification. In SDN controller, the second action is performed via Web3.js API to acquire the hash values of implemented agents in layer-1 such input data based on assessment retrieval with the defined threshold values in SDN based POX controller in central layer, which is manipulated with the help of Minimum Acceptable Fitness Rate (MAFR).

6.4.1 Deep ML and SDN Fusion approach

As shown in Figure 6.4, a deep ML-based layer is fused with central SDN based POX controller, overall, our model approach is focused on fusion capability of SDN programmability and ML-based attack classification and processing approach. Input data from agents processed in the SDN layer, which also enables the provide the training datasets based on E-commerce input private data for classification purpose of deep machine learning approach in layer-3.

Multimodal based fusion deployment is already ongoing in machine learning [145]. Multiple fusion methods have been developed in the literary works for the fusion of several models equipped utilising deep learning-based approaches. Two major forms of fusion strategies exist such as late fusion, where the fused model is extracted relying on the observations provided from each experiment; and early features based fusion, wherein the experiment fusion relies on the conditional characteristic vectors that are suggested by each variable during the training of the model [37]. Since machine learning provides outstanding performance at feature extraction and their interpretation, initial fusion has been considered to be the best methodology and has demonstrated state-of-the-art performance in combining deep learning techniques with other developers such as SDN and agents and so on [95]. However, deep

learning implementation in E-commerce provides a feasible and effective approach to handle and process larger input data, which converts original data structure into a higher-level representation with minimum overhead also retaining rational overhead computing and storage. The authors of [29] has also proposed a model based on deep machine learning to acquire feasible and effective attack detection results. In our proposed model of the E-commerce trust model in SDN, we have utilised the features based early fusion strategy with deep machine learning in SDN context under these considerations:

1. Deep machine learning is used to classify attacks non-attacks and trust and distrust in E-commerce applications following by SDN collected data.
2. Trust-based agents are used to providing secure and reliable communications between sellers and their potential buyers with Ethereum technology.
3. All input data collected and processed with the help of the SDN POX controller unit to manage and manipulate for the classification of the attack at a deep ML layer.

However, we utilise a deep learning model of X_k with the unlabelled dataset given as $x = (x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n)$, where first input layer of model of X_k with n numbers of neurons to encode the input values is provided as below in equation 6.7

$$H_1 = F(w_x x + b_1) \tag{6.7}$$

Whereas, the values of F represents the activation function with the help of w_1, b_1 weighted encoding metric and biased values respectively. The activation is performed between input and hidden layers of the deep machine learning model. Our model's activation function such as Sigmoid activation function is provided as below in equation 6.8

Figure 6.4: based E-commerce Fusion Attack Detection Model in SDN

$$F_{(z)} = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-z)} \quad (6.8)$$

Output generated from the first hidden layer (h_1) of deep machine learning model is used as input for the second hidden layer (h_2) for the purpose of training the datasets with the help of w_2, b_2 values. The (h_2) represents the extracted features, which are used for second hidden layer of deep machine learning model. Training process is repeated until it reaches to the N^{th} conditional values of h_n hidden layer, which helps to train the parameters up to W_n . Hidden layer of h_n feed forwards extracted features to final N^{th} layer in model of X_k . However, in model of X_k , utilises the $W = (w_1, w_2, w_3, ..w_n)$ as weighted matrix values, also, model uses bias vector values such as $b = (b_1, b_2, b_3, ..b_n)$

In our model of X_k , all parameters are manipulated and processed with the help of

gradient descent algorithm to train all input dataset to citepehrson2018machine, which mathematically is provided in the following equations 6.9 and 6.10.

$$w_1(p+1) = w_{1,p} - \beta \frac{\theta}{\theta \times w_1} \times J(w_1, b_1) \quad (6.9)$$

$$b_1(p+1) = b_{1,p} - \beta \frac{\theta}{\theta \times b_1} \times J(w_1, b_1) \quad (6.10)$$

In gradient descent algorithm, maximum values of iterations are denoted with p , and maximum values of learning rate are represented by θ . J describes the loss function, where the loss of our model is lower down with the help of stochastic gradient descent approach. Our model X_k utilises all above-mentioned procedures for the purpose of training and evaluating attacks in E-commerce proposed model.

6.4.2 Attack Detection Approach

Depending on the intrusion proposed technique of the previous section, this protection component is responsible for efficiently establishing the necessary flow entries via the Control plane to alert the switch of the appropriate action in the circumstance of an anomaly. Anomaly incidents on the E-commerce infrastructure can be categorised into four broad categories: (a) Remote to Local (R2L): Where an intruder mimics as a specific device and seeks to connect a victim's router or host computer; (b) User to Root (U2R): Whereby an attacker may increase his / her authority from restricted root access by incorporating different conventional exploitation methods, like malicious payload and accused of stealing credentials; (c) Denial of Service (DoS): Which always exploits individual user access to the device and tries to render the denial of service to the consumer; (d) Probe: In which an attacker examines a device or host operation and seeks to collect knowledge about

the network. Our architecture of detecting attacks relies on certain input features to determine suitable flow rules for minimising such malicious activity.

Based on the NSL-KDD dataset [135], our proposed model mainly relies on four different features of data input via name, type of dataset which are provided in the Table 6.1, where have used important dataset features to avoid redundancy. In Table 6.1, host-based data are assigned with 1–10, and time-based data assigned 11–19. In contrast, more detailed level and basic features are provided in 20–31 and 32–41. In consideration of the input components, the rules-setting mechanism includes three main cases: (1) where an attack detection system detects traffic flow as regular traffic, the control plane establishes rule changes for notifying the transfer to shift traffic flow either malicious or benign; (2) whether the traffic flow is defined as a problematic or a threat stream; the Control plane shall apply a series of instructions. At first, the switch is ordered to completely disable illegal traffic with minimal impact. Second, blacklisting is used for the root of the threat. Besides, the SDN controller is modified with both the blacklisted input to implement blacklisting at a maximum standard, which stops the intruder from impacting several systems in the E-commerce-based applications. The revised rules in SDN controller often avoid circumstances in which such kinds of devices are under threat; (3) If the sequence of flow of traffic is not identified by the proposed technique, also a detailed investigation of the traffic flow is needed and the switch is alerted by the Control plane to reduce the traffic flow in order to mitigate the effect of suspicious behaviour.

6.5 Experimental Evaluation

In this section, we discuss the findings of the performance evaluation for our proposed design. Throughout our proposed system, we also utilised Mininet [107] is also used as an emulator to simulate open vSwitches and multiple usable terminals, such as E-commerce modules. In Linux OS, we implemented Mininet to create

Table 6.1: Input Feature Extraction for Attack Detection

Traffic Features for Hosts		
1	No of dst-host-(count)	Numeric-values
2	No of dst-host (srv_error_rate)	Numeric-values
3	No of dst-host (srv_count)	Numeric-values
4	No of dst-host-(error_rate)	Numeric-values
5	No of dst-host (same_srv_rate)	Numeric-values
6	No of dst-host (srv_serror_rate)	Numeric-values
7	No of dst-host (diff_srv_rat)	Numeric-values
8	No of dst-host (serror_rate)	Numeric-values
9	No of dst-host (same_src_port)	Numeric-values
10	No dst-host (srv_diff_rate)	Numeric-values
Traffic Features based on Time		
11	No srv-diff (host_rate)	
12	No of srv-diff (srv_count)	Numeric-values
13	No of srv-diff (count)	Numeric-values
14	No of srv-diff diffsrv_rate	Numeric-values
15	No of srv-diff (serror_rate)	Numeric-values
16	No of srv-diff (same_srv_rate),	Numeric-values
17	No of srv-diff (srv_error_rate)	Numeric-values
18	No of srv-diff (srv_error_rate)	Numeric-values
19	No of srv-diff (error _{rate})	Numeric-values
Traffic Features Contents		
20	No of (logged_in)	Binary-values
21	No of (guest_login)	Binary-values
22	No of (host_login)	Binary-values
23	No of (failed_logins)	Binary-values
24	No of (outbound_cmds)	Binary-values
25	No of (compromised_port)	Binary-values
26	No of (access_files)	Numeric-values
27	No of (root_shell)	Numeric-values
28	No of (shells)	Numeric-values
29	No of (su_attempts)	Numeric-values
30	No of (file_creation)	Numeric-values
31	No of (dst_root)	Numeric-values
Basic traffic features		
32	No of (Protocol_type)	Numeric-values
33	No of (Service_type)	Numeric-values
34	No of (Flag Nominal)	Numeric-values
35	No of (src_bytes)	Numeric-values
36	No of (Duration)	Numeric-values
37	No of (dst_bytes)	Numeric-values
38	No of (src_bytes)	Numeric-values
38	No of (wrong_fragment)	Numeric-values
39	No of (total_fragment)	Numeric-values
40	No of (ttl)	Numeric-values

3 workstations as virtual instances, in which the setup of each desktop included 3GB of DDR-4 RAM and an Intel i7 CPU 6th Generation. POX (Noxrepo, 2017) is deployed as main SDN-controller for the implementation of E-commerce various components, such as rules and policies to update and maintain various components, also SDN supports to the machine learning classification for the analysis of traffic activity for the identification of attacks. Controllers are operated on independent virtual machines hosted on a Linux server. We deployed the E-commerce architecture using the Ethereum platform, in which an oracle is utilised via the proposed block by using the Ethereum Interface in broadcast mode [93]. In the analytical evaluation, we considered that the SDN-controller would trigger data-driven activities adaptively. At regular intervals, each data-driven task acquires traffic from layer-1 and then forward to attack classification layer-3, which is decoupled with a deep machine learning approach to classify the traffic as benign or attack. This regular interval actively continues to classify attacks based on SDN programmability and attack fusion approach. We evaluated and validated our blockchain-based E-commerce trust model with the help the NSL-KDD dataset, which is known as an intrusion prevention dataset [135]. Private NSL-KDD statistics also comprise both benign and malicious trends of E-commerce traffic.

The effectiveness of the proposed framework is assessed in terms of various parameters, including Accuracy or F-Score, confusion matrix via True Positive (TP), True Negative (TN), False Positive (FP), False Negative (FN). which are the most relevant attack detection evaluation metrics [29].

On the basis of the above parameters, firstly we analysed our model then compared overall performance the proposed blockchain in SDN based E-commerce trust model with different scenarios. Moreover, our proposed deep learning paradigm in the SDN POX controller effectively classifies the input traffic from E-commerce applications, this approach is deployed as a centralised based trust model. Based on metrics evaluations and calculations, our proposed model in the SDN context achieves su-

Figure 6.5: Simulation of Different Attack Scenario

perior results for providing trust between seller and buyers nodes inside E-commerce application such as eBay and Amazon.

6.6 Results Evaluation with Different Attack Scenarios

We have utilised three different attack scenarios in our proposed work to evaluate the overall performance of each E-commerce node attack detection with the collaboration of in the SDN context. The evaluation of all three attack use cases is carried after blockchain-based trust function key distribution across all nodes. Three different attack scenarios are Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS), ICMP flooding,

and TCP flooding. In Figure 6.5, we have provided the network topology overview to simulate the attacks between E-commerce nodes, where A, B, and C are used as three E-commerce nodes, and D represent attackers node to launch the DDoS, ICMP flooding, and TCP flooding attacks on A, B, and C.

6.6.1 DDoS Attack Scenario

In our proposed model, attacking node D compromising all three E-commerce nodes such as A, B, and C via triggering the DDoS flooding attacks. The node D, as a DDoS attacker, compromise the E-commerce nodes such as A, B, and C with different time slots and bandwidth consumption, node A performs as botnet activity with node B, similarly, node B also launches a botnet attack with node C after being compromised by DDoS attack from D node.

In Figure 6.6, it can be seen that E-comm-1, E-comm-2, and E-comm-3, nodes stood normal at the initial 20 seconds of time with bandwidth, which is consumed around 0.3 Mbps average. Suddenly bandwidth is rapidly increasing from 0.3 Mbps to 0.8 Mbps after $t = 20$ sec once the E-comm-1 node is under DDoS attack. Then, E-comm-2 is compromised via DDoS attacks, soon after bandwidth also rapidly rises from 0.2 Mbps to 0.9 Mbps at $t = 22$ sec. In the E-comm-3 node, during the launch of DDoS floods node bandwidth reaches 0.7 Mbps from 0.4Mbps at $t = 24$ seconds. Overall, it can be observed that after implementation of trust evaluation mechanisms such as trust function key distribution between E-commerce nodes, all three nodes consume around an average of 0.3 Mbps only which does not occur in heavier network overhead. Once these nodes are under attack of DDoS floods then each node reaches an average of 0.7 Mbps this flow is sent to the attack fusion model of deep machine learning classifiers to classify the attacks and help to mitigate or block such flows.

6.6.2 ICMP Flood Attack Scenario

Attacking node D compromising all three E-commerce nodes such as A, B, and C with the help of the ICMP flooding attacks. The node D acts as ICMP flooding attacks to compromise the nodes A, B, and C with different time slots and bandwidth consumption. All compromised nodes after ICMP floods ping each other with a large volume of data adversely. During the simulation of ICMP floods, we limited total bandwidth up to 1 Mbps to be allocated and shared between A, B, and C nodes.

In Figure 6.7, it can be seen that E-comm-1, E-comm-2, and E-comm-3, nodes remain normal at the initial 15 seconds, the bandwidth is consumed less than 0.2 Mbps when there are not any ICMP flooding attacks. Moreover, during the ICMP attacks, E-comm-1 node bandwidth is exponentially rising from 0.1 Mbps to 0.7 Mbps at $t = 16$ sec. Then, E-comm-2 is compromised via the same attacks, soon after bandwidth also rapidly rises from 0 Mbps to nearly 1.0 Mbps at $t = 25$ sec. In the E-comm-3 node, bandwidth reaches 0.8 Mbps from less than 0.1 Mbps at $t = 14$ seconds.

6.6.3 TCP Flood Attack Scenario

During TCP Flood attacks, attacking node D also compromising all three E-commerce nodes such as A, B, and C by different time slots and bandwidth consumption. During the simulation of TCP flood. A, B, and C send a larger volume of TCP SYN floods to each other, which can lead to massive traffic congestion due to this fact we limited total bandwidth up to 1 Mbps to be allocated and shared between A, B, and C nodes so that our proposed model can effectively detect the malicious flow and propagates to the attack detection model.

In Figure 6.8, it can be seen that E-comm-1, E-comm-2, and E-comm-3, nodes

Figure 6.6: E-commerce Nodes under DDoS Flood Attacks

stood normal at the initial 22 seconds, where bandwidth consumption was around 0.7 Mbps average. When TCP SYN was simulated all nodes bandwidth deviated and started to decline, the E-comm-1 node during TCP Flood attack declined to 0.1 Mbps from 0.7 Mbps at $t = 25$ sec. Then, E-comm-2 and E-comm-3 after the same attacks suddenly decreased rises from 0.7 Mbps to an average of 0.1 Mbps at $t = 25$ sec respectively.

6.6.4 ML Classification

Our attack detection and mitigation model utilises the Stochastic Gradient Descent classifier. The Stochastic Gradient Descent classifier is implemented with the help of an open-source XGBOOST library, which supports model development with the help of Python based implementation. Once the nodes A, B, and C are under attack of DDoS attacks, ICMP floods, and TCP floods respectively then such malicious flows of our input traffic are sent to the attack fusion model of deep machine learning classifiers to classify the attacks and help to mitigate or block such flows. We have

Figure 6.7: E-commerce Nodes under ICMP Flood Attacks.

Figure 6.8: E-commerce Nodes under TCP Flood Attacks

Figure 6.9: Binary Confusion Matrix of All Attacks

used aggregated data such as DDoS attacks, ICMP floods, and TCP floods with 122,240 total packets for training and 29,759 packets for testing with an 80% to 20% rule.

Stochastic Gradient Descent classifier utilises well-known metrics like F1-score, precision score, and recall to evaluate the overall performance of DDoS attacks, ICMP floods, and TCP floods, these attacks detection metrics are very useful for the goodness of Stochastic Gradient Descent classifier detection rate. We have evaluated our fusion detection layer with the help of confusion matrix, related parameters, and entries for confusion matrix are provided as below:

- **True Positive (TP)** – These values represent the correctly identified attack

entries.

- **True Negative (TN)** - These values represent the correctly identified non-attacks entries.
 - **False Positive (FP)** - These values represent the incorrectly identified attack entries.
 - **False Negative (FN)**- These values represent the incorrectly identified non-attacks entries.
1. **Precision (P)** -These values represent the correctly identified attack entries that belong to correct entries:

$$Precision(P) = \frac{TP}{(TP + FP)} \quad (6.11)$$

2. **Recall (R)** - These values represent correct predictions derived from the positive entries:

$$Recall(R) = \frac{TP}{(TP + FN)} \quad (6.12)$$

3. **F1-Score** - These values represent the aggregate score to provide balance related to Precision (P) values and Recall (R) values, it is calculated by harmonic mean between Precision (P) values and Recall (R) values. The F1-Score represents the overall model accuracy and feasibly used for classification:

$$F1 - Score = \frac{2}{\frac{1}{(P+R)}} \quad (6.13)$$

In this chapter, we have utilised the above-mentioned performance metrics with the help of Stochastic Gradient Descent classifier, we combined all attacks such as DDoS attacks, ICMP floods, and TCP floods to evaluate the attack detection rate

in our proposed based trust aware E-commerce model. We run this classifier several times by merging benign traffic with different traffic rate such as 60% to 70% with all three attacks types such as DDoS attacks, ICMP floods, and TCP floods.

In Figure 6.9, it can be seen that Stochastic Gradient Descent classifier has detected attacks with 94% detection rate of F1-score, the model FP rate is also very low, FP rate is stood at 0.089% and FN rate stood at 0.072%. This shows that in SDN context, fusion attack detection model with the help of blockchain-based trust key function distribution has higher accuracy for detection with less than 0.089% false triggers.

6.6.5 Computation Resources with and without Blockchain

In our proposed model of SDN, the blockchain-based trust aware model in E-commerce applications, we have calculated the different Memory and CPU overhead of DDoS attacks, ICMP floods, and TCP floods during operation and without operation. We observed additional memory and CPU overhead during operation in our proposed model.

In Figure 6.10, average memory consumption during DDoS attacks increases from 70% to 82%, when we run services and applications, similarly average CPU also rises by nearly 10%. During ICMP Flooding attacks, the average memory consumption increases from 61% to 73% with services and application, similarly average CPU also rises from 75% to 84%. During TCP Flooding attacks, the average memory consumption increases from 77% to 86%, when we run services and application, similarly average CPU also rises from 8% overall.

Moreover, we can observe that blockchain-based trust aware model in E-commerce applications has significant higher detection accuracy and minimum computational overhead, such as during services and apply our model only receive nearly 10% more

Figure 6.10: Memory and CPU Overhead for Different Attack Scenario

memory overhead and nearly 7% of CPU, which is acceptable and feasible due to higher detection accuracy in larger E-commerce applications.

6.7 Summary

In the proposed study, we utilize the SDN programmability approaches in collaboration with Blockchain and machine learning. The proposed model consists of three layers such as Layer-1 uses the ECC private keys and public keys distribution between the sellers and buyers of E-commerce applications for security and trust improvement. Layer-2 is created with an SDN POX controller, this layer works as the central control unit, which helps to collect data from Layer-1, and also helps to update and configure the other elements of the model. Finally, Layer-3 acts as a fusion attack detection model, which collaboratively works with Layer-2 and Layer-3, where machine learning classifier such as Gradient Descent Algorithm is used to classify the attacks and non-attacks to improve the E-commerce users trust.

In this chapter, the major objective of our research is to optimize the security between various E-commerce applications/business, also to mitigate the single point failure of security vulnerabilities via Blockchain-based SDN framework. Our proposed model also utilises the trust between E-commerce applications with the help of Blockchain-based trust key distribution. Overall, our model achieves a higher detection rate with very minimum resource consumption. Overall, our evaluated results show that SDN based model outperforms centralised architecture, the proposed model also classify the attacks effectively with less time. Our results also recommend that this proposed design can be implemented in larger and distributed E-commerce network to detect malicious activities and improve the trust factor.

Chapter 7

Conclusion and Future Work

Consumers often claim a lack of confidence as a justification for not doing business with Internet vendors. As a result, trust and belief in the Internet must be promoted. In both the online and offline worlds, trust is a necessary component for a transaction to take place. Most of the region went into lockdown in March 2020, causing several companies to briefly close. Cities are increasingly loosening limits as of this report, but the future remains unclear. Also reopening companies have rules requiring social stepping away, the use of masks, and limiting the number of people who may visit a venue place at a single time. People are increasingly likely to shop online as physical shopping gets impossible, if not downright frightening. The fact that customers were still enthusiastic about Amazon and other online stores made the move even smoother. According to [35] As of April 2020, online sales had increased by 40%. In the post-quarantine era, there's a strong possibility the pattern will continue. And if department stores reopen entirely, the benefits of internet shopping can continue. All of this indicates that now is an excellent time to begin or expand your e-commerce activities. In the first and second quarters of 2020, the share of e-commerce in overall retail in the United States rose steadily (from 9.6% to 11.8%), peaking at 16.1%. The trend in the United Kingdom is comparable, with e-share commerce's of retail rising from 17.3% to 20.3% between the first and

second quarters of 2020, before rising sharply to 31.3% between the first and second quarters of 2020. There is alarming demand for creating trust for E-commerce sellers and buyers, also E-commerce applications must provide effective and reliable security to cope with the current demand of online shopping during the pandemic.

Trust is a complex concept that is impossible to establish. Each person's level of trust is different when it comes to taking the plunge and conducting online purchases. For various individuals, defining trust is challenging. The fact that people come from different cultures, have different perspectives, and have different perceptions will affect how they view trust. In e-commerce, Internet retailers and their websites may be sources of legitimacy in and of themselves. As a result, businesses must understand how to handle their customers' trust in e-commerce. Building customer interest on the Internet, however, is a concern for online companies.

Due to the fact of privacy, lack of physical contact and interaction, the E-commerce marketplace face several challenges. Physical signs that influence customers' sense of trust in legacy shopping place, comprises of the physical location of the marketplace, and face to face interaction with salespersons are missing in the online world. In the E-commerce based market due to lack of direct physical contact results in more difficulties to create trust so specially for consumers to place an order online. As a result, this poses a significant threat to E-commerce businesses. It is critical to identify factors that contribute to e-commerce customer trust. Large companies have no power over the level of trust that their clients have in them. They simply need to create cultures that promote trust. A marketplace can be believed, but only if the members believe it. Finding out what kind of variables are critical for establishing consumer trust in the online shopping world was insightful to feasibly evaluate our research. This research aimed to obtain a greater understanding of e-commerce customer trust. We tried to identify major considerations that help to build trust online by examining relevant literature on customer trust in e-commerce. We chose a few basic factors from these to motivate our observational study, in

which we wanted to see how consumers view the value of the chosen factors in their deciding to purchase online.

To improve the customer trust to place an order online, first of all, our research utilises only three different dimensions that play a significant role within E-commerce transactions, which provide the support the buyers to detect fraudulent activities. The proposed method evaluates the similarity between the new transaction and the past transactions in the products types dimension, the number of the products sold dimension and the transactions amounts dimension. This method can assist to prevent the value imbalance problem by measuring the similarity between three dimensions (contexts) and evaluating the final trust value.

In our second contribution, our model further evaluates the trust factors between the transactions by measuring the similarities between the new transactions of a purchaser and the previous sales record of a buyer in the transactions times dimension and the overall ratings dimension. The proposed model can effectively be used in E-commerce applications. It also can assist to prevent the value imbalance problem by measuring the similarity between two dimensions (contexts) and evaluating the final trust value. This strategy can be used to measure transaction trust by analyzing the correlations between a buyer's current purchases or his/her previous purchase history.

In the third contribution, our research combines all five dimensions such as the product type, the number of products sold, the transaction amount, transactions times dimension, and the seller's overall rating. In the proposed model, the main objective was to estimate the weight of every dimensions after mining comments or feedback from E-commerce users. We created an effective algorithm for mining comments or feedback from E-commerce users, then extracting input on measurements weights, integrating natural language processing methods, information extraction and subject/topic modelling. An evaluation was carried based on Amazon data sets, which enables us to demonstrate that order of importance for our predefined

dimensions is Rating, Product Type, Price, Time interval and Quantity Sold.

In our final contribution, we utilize the SDN programmability approaches in collaboration with blockchain and machine learning. The proposed model consists of three layers such as Layer-1 uses the ECC private keys and public keys distribution between the sellers and buyers of E-commerce applications for security and trust improvement. Layer-2 is created with an SDN POX controller, this layer works as the central control unit, which helps to collect data from Layer-1, and also helps to update and configure the other elements of the model. Finally, Layer-3 acts as a fusion attack detection model, which collaboratively works with Layer-2 and Layer-3, where machine learning classifier such as Gradient Descent Algorithm is used to classify the attacks and non-attacks to improve the E-commerce users trust.

In this model, the major objective of our research is to optimize the security between various E-commerce applications/business, also to mitigate the single point failure of security vulnerabilities via a Blockchain-based SDN framework. Our proposed model also utilises the trust between E-commerce applications with the help of blockchain-based trust key distribution. Overall, our model achieves a higher detection rate with very minimum resource consumption. Overall, our evaluated results show that SDN based model outperforms centralised architecture, the proposed model also classify the attacks effectively with less time. Our proposed model also utilises the trust between E-commerce applications with the help of Blockchain-based trust key distribution. Overall, our model achieves nearly a 95% attack detection rate with less than 7% false alerts, while it consumes around 10% more memory and nearly 7% of CPU overhead during full services running in lager e-commerce applications.

As future work, we will present our model with real-time big data of E-commerce application, where we deploy trust evaluation factors based on no redundant dataset, we mainly focused to evaluate trust factors based on deep machine learning without

human interaction and system updating. There are more dimensions such as the communication within the transactions, the quality of the whole transaction, and security between potential sellers and buyers that need to be considered. Overall, we focused on a more efficient model with accurate and reliable outcomes to help grow up E-commerce market exponentially. Our results also recommend that this proposed design can be implemented in larger and distributed E-commerce network to detect malicious activities and improve the trust factor.

As previously said, improvements to SDN-based credibility mechanisms are currently being worked on. More research is required to figure out how to prevent these processes from being manipulated by unethical users. If alternate conflict resolution frameworks are to raise confidence in international e-commerce, more research is required to see how successful they are in diverse regions, as well as how to use new technologies like blockchain and SDN programmability methods to build trust for smaller to larger E-commerce applications. Studying new trust-building strategies as they evolve in the private sector would also be beneficial. New forms of payment and insurance models targeted to the e-commerce market are now evolving, and it would be important to see how they become broadly accepted.

As future work, we will present our model with real-time big data of E-commerce application, where we deploy trust evaluation factors based on no redundant dataset, we mainly focused to evaluate trust factors based on deep machine learning without human interaction and system updating. There are more dimensions such as time to handle the transaction, the quality of the transaction, and security between potential sellers and buyers need to be considered. Overall, we focused on more efficient model with accurate and reliable outcomes to help grow up E-commerce market exponentially. Our results also recommend that this proposed design can be implemented in larger and distributed E-commerce network to detect malicious activities and improve the trust factor.

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